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**WP3 – Determination of drug transfer and infant drug exposure during lactation:
generation of quantitative and translatable data**

D3.10 Optimized protocol for non-clinical data generation regarding drug milk excretion and breastfed infant drug exposure

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List of abbreviations

AUC	Area under the curve
CL	Clearance
CMC	Chemistry, Manufacturing and Controls
CHMP	Committee for Medicinal Products for Human Use (EU)
DID	Daily infant dosage
EMA	European Medicines Agency (EU)
EDTA	Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid
FDA	Food and Drug Administration (USA)
GOF	Goodness-of-fit
HA	Health Authority
hMEC	Human Mammary Epithelial Cells
IMI	Innovative Medicines Initiative
ITF	Innovation Task Force
mAb	Monoclonal Antibody
MEC	Mammary Epithelial Cells
M/P	Milk to Plasma
NDA	New Drug Application (USA)
Papp	Apparent Permeability coefficient
OFV	Objective function value
PBPK	Physiology-Based Pharmacokinetic(s)
PD	Pharmacodynamics
PK	Pharmacokinetics
SID	Semel in die
RID	Relative infant dose
TOC	Table of Contents
VPC	Visual Predictive Checks
WP	Work Package

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1 Abstract

This Deliverable summarizes the results obtained by WP3 on the development of a platform of non-clinical models (‘tools’) to predict human milk drug concentrations and subsequent exposure of nursing infants to maternal medication.

The non-clinical model systems developed and evaluated all employ methodologies to quantitatively assess the passage of small molecule medicines across the blood milk barrier. The underlying hypothesis is indeed that the ability of a compound to cross this barrier will ultimately determine the milk concentrations of that compound (Ventrella et al., 2019; Nauwelaerts et al., 2021).

The complete non-clinical platform could be applied both during early and late phases of drug development, but also after a marketing authorization has been granted.

Currently, there is no well-developed non-clinical model that is accepted by the health authorities that can be used by the pharmaceutical companies and researchers to predict medicine secretion into human milk. Of the standard reproductive toxicology studies that are conducted during the development of a new drug candidate, the pre- and postnatal developmental toxicity study is the only one that includes a lactation phase. However, this toxicity study provides only limited information regarding lactation, since no quantitative data are collected for the potential medicine transfer into milk. If a dedicated milk transfer study is conducted in rats, it can be helpful in determining the “presence” or “absence” of a medicine into the milk, but due to species-specific differences in lactation physiology, animal lactation data typically do not reliably predict quantitative levels in human milk. Therefore, an estimation of the relevant infant dose (RID) is not possible. Consequently, at the time of new medicine approval, limited or no information is available that can be used to adequately inform women on the safety and the proper use of the medicine while nursing their infant. In most of the cases, the medicine’s label will recommend to the woman not to breastfeed while taking the medication due to the absence of data. This situation poses significant challenges for both the mother and the infant. The lack of appropriate information could deprive the infant of important benefits of breastfeeding, such as optimal nutrition and antibodies for protection from illnesses and diseases. Additionally, for many women, breastfeeding increases both physical and emotional bonding with their infant.

The proposed non-clinical platform would allow a more reliable prediction of medicine concentrations in human milk along with systemic exposure in breastfed infants during drug development, especially since human data on breastfeeding is typically not available at marketing authorization. In addition, the methods developed in this platform may be taken into consideration towards adoption into regulatory guidelines for the use of medicines during lactation.

Results obtained in this non-clinical platform/workflow are expected to facilitate a risk assessment and labeling of a medicine candidate, as well as the creation of a basis to advise women who would like to breastfeed. Importantly, pharmacokinetic information obtained in the proposed non-clinical platform will need to be merged with toxicodynamic information for the specific compound.

In the context of this work package, small molecule drugs have been selected to be in-scope. Amoxicillin (antibiotic), cetirizine (antihistamine), metformin (anti-diabetic), and venlafaxine (antidepressant) are the four medicines selected for investigation in both WP3 and WP4 (see Section 2, Tables 1 and 2, for more information on compound selection). In addition, WP3 will generate non-clinical data in the *in vivo* minipig model for valaciclovir, levetiracetam, escitalopram and atenolol, as well as investigate several additional model compounds in the *in vitro* model and PBPK models (see below). Future work could expand the use of this non-clinical platform to other therapeutic modalities.

The development of this non-clinical platform encompasses three distinct methodologies that may be used either independently or together depending on the development stage of the medicine in question.

Figure 1-1 11Non-clinical platform encompassing three distinct methodologies to determine medicine transfer into human milk and predict potential infant exposure.

Note: Graphical abstract modified from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopha.2020.111038> and created using [Biorender.com](https://www.biorender.com)

The three methodologies are:

1. **State-of-the-art *in vitro* models** that are representative of the blood milk barrier and can be used for accurate and rapid determination of plasma-milk transfer rates (permeability coefficients) of medicines and drug candidates across this blood-milk barrier. The *in vitro* model can be used early in drug development to calculate the extent to which a drug will cross the mammary epithelium, enter the milk, and be available to a nursing infant. These permeability coefficients will be converted to clearance values for milk secretion, which can then be used as data input for drug-specific lactation PBPK models. In addition, the utility of implementing these permeability coefficients in *in vitro* to *in vivo* extrapolation (IVIVE) algorithms for the M/P ratio will be explored.
2. An **animal lactation model** in lactating Göttingen Minipig sows to determine maternal systemic exposure, milk drug concentration, and infant systemic medicine concentrations, which can be

used as a prediction of the human maternal and infant exposure to a medicine. The *in vivo* model will also enable the generation of maternal systemic PK data and maternal milk drug concentrations. Furthermore, infant systemic drug concentrations resulting from exposure via breast milk can be determined. Together these data can allow for the calculation of a relative infant dose. Combined with known toxicity data from the development of the drug, recommendations for safe use during lactation could be provided in the label.

3. **Physiologically-Based Pharmacokinetic (PBPK) models** for predicting drug concentration time profiles in the blood and milk of lactating women, as well as pediatric PBPK models to predict systemic exposure of breastfed infants to the maternal medication. These predictions will better inform the label on safe use of medicines during lactation.

The method(s) chosen will be dependent on the stage of medicine development, and/or the amount of (pre)clinical data available for the medicine (candidate). Consequently, the workflow will be customized for each medicine. The outcomes would enable risk assessment and could be used to inform labelling recommendations for the safe use of the medicine during lactation. Since this non-clinical platform allows to generate medicine-specific quantitative data, an estimated relative infant dose may also be calculated.

IMI ConcePTION is also seeking EMA Qualification Advice of this innovative non-clinical platform for the reliable prediction of medicine concentrations in human milk and an estimation of the systemic exposure in breastfed infants.

2 Methods

2.1 Model compounds

The selection of at least ten model compounds was described in detail in *D3.1 Report* on scope and limitations of *in vivo* and *in vitro* non-clinical and computational models for drug milk excretion and infant systemic exposure; Selection of a panel of at least 10 model compounds for initial evaluation of non-clinical models. In addition, caffeine was added because of its relevance and availability of clinical data. As highlighted above, the consortium decided to not include biological compounds at this stage.

As mentioned before, Work Package 4 is establishing a self-sustaining human milk and blood biobank and analytical center, capable of measuring medication concentrations in milk. Several human lactation studies have been conducted, and the results of these studies were used by WP3 in comparison to the *in vivo* minipig data to see how well the animal model can predict the maternal blood and milk drug concentration. The model medicines selected in WP4 were also used by WP3 for the *in vivo* model.

The selection criteria for the model compounds in WP4 were based on the following:

1. Availability of human data.
2. Diverse therapeutic areas.
3. Diverse physicochemical properties.
4. Societal impact of data generation.
5. Ability to assess PK.
6. Existence of networks to raise awareness for patients to participate in research and to develop ethical standards via empirical qualitative studies (i.e. patient groups).

7. Patient compliance.
8. Feasibility to recruit a sufficient sample size for popPK analysis.
9. Analytical feasibility.

The selection criteria for the additional model compounds in WP3 were:

1. Diverse chemical structures and physicochemical properties.
2. Clinical relevance in the lactating population.
3. Quality and resolution of available reference data.
4. Availability of popPK for breast milk exposure.
5. Availability of PK data.

The model medicines selected in WP4 are shown in Table 2-1. To increase the overall number and diversity of model medicines used in WP3 for the *in vitro* and PBPK models, additional medicines were selected and are shown in Table 2-2.

Table 2-1 Model medicines evaluated in both WP4 and WP3

Medicine	MW	BCS Class	pKa	LogP	fu	Main Elimination Route
Amoxicillin	365	I	3.23 (acid) 7.43 (base)	0.87	0.85	Renal
Cetirizine	389	III	2.9 (acid) 8.0 (base) 2.2 (base)	1.50	0.07	Renal
Metformin	129	III	12.40 (base)	-1.43	1.00	Renal
Venlafaxine	277	I	9.5 (base)	2.9	0.73	Hepatic (CYP2D6)

Molecular weight (MW, g/mol); biopharmaceutical classification system (BCS); acid dissociation constant (pKa); lipophilicity as Log₁₀ of the partition coefficient between octanol and water (LogP); fraction unbound in human plasma (fu).

Table 2-2 Model medicines additionally evaluated in WP3, illustrating a diversity in physicochemical and pharmacokinetic properties

Medicine	MW	BCS Class	pKa	LogP	fu	Main Elimination Route
Caffeine	194	I	0.80 (base)	-0.07	0.70	Hepatic (CYP1A2)
Levetiracetam	170	I	- (neutral)	-0.60	0.90	Renal & esterase
Nevirapine	266	II	2.8 (base)	1.93	0.40	Hepatic (CYP3A4)
Sertraline	306	II	9.43 (base)	5.5	0.023	Hepatic (CYPs)
Tacrolimus	804	II	9.95 (acid)	2.7	0.99	Hepatic (CYP3A4)
Tenofovir	287	III	1.35 (acid) 6.70 (acid) 3.80 (base)	1.87	0.993	Renal
Valproic acid	144	I	4.80 (acid)	2.75	0.14	Hepatic (UGTs)
Zidovudine	267	I	9.7 (acid)	0.05	0.80	Hepatic (UGT2B7)

Molecular weight (MW, g/mol); Biopharmaceutics Classification System (BCS); acid dissociation constant (pKa); lipophilicity as Log₁₀ of the partition coefficient between octanol and water (LogP); fraction unbound in human plasma (fu).

2.2 *In vitro* models representative of the blood milk barrier

In vitro cell culture models can be used to study the transfer of medicines into the milk based on the reasonable assumption that the mammary epithelium forms the main barrier between maternal blood and milk (Ventrella et al., 2019).

For this purpose, a selection of human cell lines MCF-7 (Andersson et al., 2017), PMC-42LA (Freestone et al., 2014), MCF-10A (Qu et al., 2015), as well as primary human mammary epithelial cells (hMECs) (Kimura et al., 2006) were investigated. The cells were cultured on Transwell™ inserts. Different culture conditions have been explored. Primary cells are the most *in vivo*-relevant model, but they have a limited life span and are more difficult to culture compared to cell lines. Therefore, both primary cells and cell lines have been investigated as possible *in vitro* model. Eventually, the hMEC-based model proved to yield the best results and was selected for further development and evaluation.

Furthermore, the use of primary minipig mammary epithelial cells (mpMECs) as basis for an *in vitro* model representative for medicine transport across the minipig blood-milk barrier is currently being used within ConcePTION WP3. This way, it will be possible to directly compare the *in vitro* findings with the results obtained in the *in vivo* minipig model. Such comparison can provide unique insights in preferred strategies for *in vitro* to *in vivo* extrapolation (IVIVE) for this type of data. The combination of the data obtained in the *in vitro* and *in vivo* animal models will indeed lead to mechanistic insights and scaling information that could also be applied to the human *in vitro* model. This will ultimately enhance the predictive performance of the (human) PBPK models as well.

First, culture protocols were optimised for the human primary cells (hMECs) and cell lines (MCF-7, MCF-10A and PMC42-LA). Ethical approval for acquiring, passaging, storing and culturing hMECs was obtained from the Ethics Committee Research (EC Research) UZ/KU Leuven (S675546). Briefly, hMECs were cultured in serum-free mammary epithelial cell basal medium (PromoCell, Heidelberg, Germany), with 0.004 mL/mL bovine pituitary extract, 10 ng/mL epidermal growth factor, 5 µg/mL insulin (recombinant human), 0.5 µg/mL hydrocortisone and 1 % Antibiotic-antimycotic solution. Cells were subcultured at 80 % confluency (after 5-7 days), at a seeding density of 5000 cells/cm². Details about the culture of hMECs, and the culture of the cell lines can be found in *D3.3Report on characterization in vitro human/animal mammary epithelial cell culture* available including comparison between *in vitro* models and in our publication (La Mantia et al., 2024).

Subsequently, after the isolation, mpMECs were cultured in DMEM/F-12 + Glutamax medium, with addition of 10 % FBS, 5 ng/mL dermal growth factor, 5 µg/mL insulin, 0.5 µg/mL hydrocortisone and 1 % antibiotic-antimycotic solution, following the procedure described in *D3.3-Report*. Cells were subcultured at 80 % confluency (after 3-4 days), at a seeding density of 20 000 cells/cm².

As a next step, the team aimed to characterise the selected *in vitro* models. Poor characterization has remained one of the main gaps of the cell culture models that are currently described in literature. Therefore, the team performed a thorough and in-depth characterization of the selected *in vitro* models (hMEC and mpMEC).

First, the monolayer integrity after seeding the cells on Transwell™ inserts was evaluated via measurement of TransEpithelial Electrical Resistance (TEER) and transport of the passive ‘paracellular pathway’ probe fluorescein. A cut-off TEER value of 200 Ohm.cm² was selected, based on what has been found in literature for hMECs (Kimura et al., 2009). The monolayer integrity was evaluated after applying diverse culture conditions for the cells on the Transwell inserts. The monolayer integrity experiments have been performed for both the primary cells (hMECS and mpMECs) and the cell lines (MCF-7, MCF-10A and PMC42-LA). The results indicated that the cell lines did not reproducibly form a tight monolayer. Together with the fact that primary cells are the most *in vivo* biorelevant model, this has formed the basis for selection of the primary cells as *in vitro* model for the blood milk barrier. Optimal results for hMECs and mpMECs were obtained through using a PET membrane in 24-well plate (0.3 cm² pore size 0.4 µm code 353095). Briefly, cells were seeded on Transwell inserts at a density of 333 333 or 500 000 cells/cm², for hMECs and mpMECs respectively. For hMECs, a full growth medium supplemented with 10% FBS was utilized to achieve maturation on Transwell inserts. mpMECs were cultured with full growth medium alone. A tight monolayer was formed after 35 days of culture for hMECs, whereas it took 4 days for mpMECS Detailed information about the monolayer integrity experiments can be found in *D3.3-Report* and in the following publication (Bernardini et al., 2024; La Mantia et al., 2024).

Secondly, cell morphology was assessed via light microscopy, while the staining of cytokeratins and E-cadherin was used to confirm the epithelial phenotype. For this purpose, hMECs and mpMECS were cultured for 35 and 4 days, respectively, on transwell inserts. The cells were then washed with PBS and fixed with 4 % paraformaldehyde for 15 min at room temperature. Following fixation, the cells were washed three times with PBS, and permeabilized with 0.5 % Triton-X-100 in PBS for 10 min at room temperature. The epitopes were blocked using a solution of 10 % FBS and 0.5 % Triton-X-100 in PBS for 1 hour at room temperature. The cells were incubated overnight at 4 °C with labelled primary antibodies. On the following day, the cells were washed three times with PBS, and the membrane was cut from the transwell inserts. The membrane was then fixed on an imaging glass with a coverslip using a mounting medium containing DAPI.

Thirdly, the presence of tight junctions was confirmed through the staining of Zonula Occludens-1 and Occludin. The staining methods followed were identical to those used for cytokeratins and E-cadherin.

In addition, the transporters expressed in the model were characterised based on mRNA expression, and functional experiments, utilizing known transporter substrates. The functional assay was identical to the methods used for the application of the *in vitro* model (detailed below).

The probe substrates employed were:

- (i) atenolol for paracellular passage (and monolayer integrity).
- (ii) Propranolol for passive transcellular passage.
- (iii) Metformin for Organic Cation Transporter activity.
- (iv) Methotrexate for Organic anion transporter (OAT) activity.
- (v) Sulfasalazine for BCRP activity.
- (vi) Carboxydichlorofluorescein diacetate (CDFDA) for MRP activity.
- (vii) Fexofenadine for P-glycoprotein (P-gp; MDR1) activity.

Evaluation of these probe substrates in the *in vitro* model is expected to provide valuable insights into the suitability of the model for assessing the blood/milk passage of medicines that are substrates for the corresponding transporters. The relevance of this aspect has been previously highlighted by experts.

The selected *in vitro* models (hMECs and mpMECs) were used to determine the permeability of the human blood-milk barrier for specific medicines (i.e., application of the *in vitro* models). The *in vitro* experiments were performed after 35 days for culture for hMECs, and after 4 days for mpMECs. The culture medium was changed to fresh medium (0.3 mL in the apical chamber and 0.72 mL in the basolateral chamber) either one day or three hours prior to the experiment for hMECs and mpMECs, respectively. Individual stock solutions of the model medicines at 100 mM in DMSO were stored at -20°C. Exceptions included tenofovir, which was prepared at 10 mM in ultrapure water, and metformin, which was prepared at 100 mM in ultrapure water. Subsequently, dosing solutions with multiple medicines were prepared in transwell culture medium as follows:

1. Amoxicillin, nevirapine, valproic acid, and cetirizine.
2. Metformin, levetiracetam, tenofovir and zidovudine.
3. Venlafaxine, tacrolimus, and sertraline.
4. Caffeine.

The permeability experiments involved adding medium to the receptor compartment and the dosing solution to the donor compartment to achieve a final concentration of 50 µM for each medicine (or probe substrate) in the medium (with 0.2% DMSO). The final volumes were set to 0.5 mL in the apical compartment and 1.2 mL in the basolateral compartment. This standardized approach allowed us to generate permeability coefficients for a substantial number of model medicines.

Each dosing solution was tested using three to six inserts, depending on the specific experiment requirements. Transport experiments were performed in both directions for a duration of 2 hours, at 37 °C under movement (120 rpm). A sample was taken from each dosing solution, and receptor compartment samples (equivalent to half of the compartment volume) were collected at 30, 60 and 90 min, with an equal volume of medium added to replace the sampled volume. The dilutions due to sampling were considered for the calculation of the cumulative amount transported. At the end of the experiment (120 min), samples were taken from both the receptor and donor compartments.

Three independent experiments, each with newly seeded cells, were performed to confirm the results. The apparent permeability coefficient was calculated using Equation 1:

$$P_{app} = (dQ/dt) / (A \cdot C_0) \quad (\text{Equation 1})$$

where:

- P_{app} is the apparent permeability coefficient (cm/s)
- dQ/dt is the steady state transepithelial flux (signal/s) of the medicine
- A is the surface area of the filter (0.3 cm²)
- C_0 is the initial donor concentration (50 µM, signal/mL) of the medicine or probe substrate
- ‘Signal’ corresponds to the area-under-the-curve of the compound peak in the LC-MSMS chromatogram, corrected for dilutions made during sample preparation

Samples that fell below the lower limit of quantification were excluded for the calculation of the slope of the cumulative amount transported curve.

Transepithelial electrical resistance (TEER) was measured before and after the experiment to assess the integrity of the cellular monolayer. Measurements were taken at 37°C in the medium, using an Epithelial Volt/Ohm Meter 2 (EVOM2, World Precision Instruments). The TEER was calculated using Equation 2:

$$TEER = (R_{sample} - R_{blank}) \times A \quad (\text{Equation 2})$$

where:

- R_{sample} is the resistance of the cell monolayer (Ω),
- R_{blank} is the resistance of the blank insert without cells (Ω),
- A is the surface area of the filter (cm^2).

The integrity of the monolayer was confirmed after the experiment via measurement of sodium fluorescein transport. The medium in the apical compartment was replaced with 0.5 mL of sodium fluorescein solution (2.66 mM) prepared in transport buffer, while the basolateral compartment was filled with 1.2 mL of transport buffer. The transport buffer consisted of HBSS (Lonza), supplemented with 10 mM HEPES (VWR International) and 25 mM glucose (Thermo Fisher Scientific). Sodium fluorescein transport was determined after 1 hour, at 37°C under gentle shaking (120 rpm). A sample was taken from the basolateral compartment after 1 hour. The concentration of sodium fluorescein in the samples was measured via fluorescence intensity ($\lambda = 490/524 \text{ nm}$) using a Tecan Infinite M200 plate reader (Tecan Group Ltd., Männedorf, Austria). Transport buffer was used as a blank, and a calibration curve was prepared with sodium fluorescein concentrations ranging from 207.8 nM (0.0078 %) to 3.325 μM (0.125 %). The transport of sodium fluorescein (%) was calculated using Equation 3:

$$\text{Transport}_{\text{sodium fluorescein}}(\%) = \frac{\text{Concentration}_{\text{sample}} (\mu\text{M}) \times \text{Volume}_{\text{basolateral}} (\text{mL})}{\text{Concentration}_{\text{donor}} (\mu\text{M}) \times \text{Volume}_{\text{apical}} (\text{mL})} \times 100 \% \quad (\text{Equation 3})$$

The implementation of the Papp values into a PBPK model will require *in vitro* to *in vivo* extrapolation (IVIVE). Several methods were considered to derive a (generic) scaling factor for this purpose, including:

- comparison between *in vitro* and *in vivo* data** generated for at least 4 model compounds using minipig models; this method will be evaluated when *in vivo* data for more model compounds becomes available
- comparison between *in vitro/in silico*-based predictions and clinical lactation data** for at least 10 model compounds

This approach considers that the blood-milk barrier transepithelial clearance essentially corresponds to the product of the barrier permeability (Papp, compound specific) and the barrier surface area (mammary physiology). Notably the surface area of the mammary glands was estimated according to the model reported by Zhang et al. (2022). The impact of implementing the total surface area information in the PBPK models already designed within WP3 has been evaluated.

2.2.1 Bioanalysis

Standard solutions of test compounds at Concentrations of 50 μM , 500 nM and 5 nM were prepared by spiking stock solutions (5 mM in DMSO) of model compounds and serial dilution with transwell culture medium (as detailed in section 2 and 3). These standard samples were processed along with study samples and used for qualification of analytical runs.

The determination of model compounds in samples generated from *in vitro* experiments was based on LC-MS/MS analysis using Shimadzu LCMS-8050 system (Shimadzu, Japan) equipped with an electrospray ionization (ESI) source. For the analysis of the study samples, four distinct analytical methods and sample preparation workflows were developed and verified, each tailored to separate analyses of four different mixtures of model compounds.

A. Method for amoxicillin, nevirapine, valproic acid, and cetirizine

Sample Preparation: 50 μL of study sample was mixed with 200 μL of 0.1% formic acid in methanol. The mixture was centrifuged at 12000 rpm for 10 min at 21°C. Then, 100 μL of the supernatant was mixed with 100 μL of water in a 96-well plate. 1 μL (for donor samples) or 10 μL (for receiver samples) was injected for analysis.

Chromatographic separation was carried out on a Phenomenex Kinetex® C8 (100 x 2.1 mm, 2.6 μm) column at 40°C. The autosampler temperature was set at 15°C. The mobile phase consisted of a gradient mixture of a) 10 mM ammonium acetate and b) methanol. The flow rate was 0.4 mL/min and the run time was 6.5 min. MS detection was performed at positive mode using ionizing voltage of 4 kV, except for valproic acid at negative mode with ionizing voltage of 3 kV. The interface temperature was set at 300°C and desolvation line temperature at 250°C, with ultrahigh-purity nitrogen for the drying gas (10 L/min), nebulizer gas (3 L/min) and heating gas (10 L/min). Multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) was carried out for amoxicillin, nevirapine and cetirizine using argon as collision gas (CID), with a dwell time of 50 msec for each transition. Selected ion monitoring (SIM) was used for determining valproic acid. MRM transition or SIM target ion, and CID for each analyte are shown in Table 3.

B. Method for metformin, levetiracetam, tenofovir and zidovudine

Sample Preparation: 50 μL of study sample was mixed with 200 μL of acetonitrile. The mixture was centrifuged at 16260 g for 10 min at 21°C. Then, 100 μL of the supernatant was mixed with 100 μL of water in a 96-well plate. 1 μL (for donor samples) or 10 μL (for receiver samples) was injected for analysis.

Chromatographic separation was carried out on an Phenomenex Luna Omega® Polar C18 (50 x 2.1 mm, 1.6 μm) column at 40°C. The autosampler temperature was set at 15°C. The mobile phase consisted of gradient mixture of a) 0.1% formic acid in water and b) 0.1% formic acid in acetonitrile. The flow rate was 0.4 mL/min, and the run time was 6.5 min. MS detection was performed at positive mode using ionizing voltage of 4 kV. The interface temperature was set at 300°C and desolvation line temperature at 250°C, with ultrahigh-purity nitrogen for the drying gas (10 L/min), nebulizer gas (3 L/min) and heating gas (10 L/min). Multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) was carried out using argon as collision gas (CID),

with a dwell time of 50 msec for each transition. MRM transition and CID for each analyte are shown in Table 3.

C. Method for venlafaxine, tacrolimus, and sertraline

Sample Preparation: 50 μL of study sample was mixed with 200 μL of methanol. The mixture was centrifuged at 12000 rpm for 10 min at 21°C. Then, 100 μL of the supernatant was mixed with 100 μL of water in a 96-well plate. 1 μL (for donor samples) or 10 μL (for receiver samples) was injected for analysis.

Chromatographic separation was carried out on an Phenomenex Luna Omega® Polar C18 (50 x 2.1 mm, 1.6 μm) column at 40°C. The autosampler temperature was set at 15°C. The mobile phase consisted of gradient mixture of a) 10 mM ammonium acetate and b) 0.1% formic acid in methanol. The flow rate was 0.4 mL/min and the run time was 5 min. MS detection was performed at positive mode using ionizing voltage of 4 kV. The interface temperature was set at 300°C and desolvation line temperature at 250°C, with ultrahigh-purity nitrogen for the drying gas (10 L/min), nebulizer gas (3 L/min) and heating gas (10 L/min). Multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) was carried out using argon as collision gas (CID), with a dwell time of 50 msec for each transition. MRM transition and CID for each analyte are shown in Table 3.

D. Method for caffeine

Sample Preparation: 50 μL of study sample was mixed with 200 μL of methanol. The mixture was centrifuged at 12000 rpm for 10 min at 21°C. Then, 100 μL of the supernatant was mixed with 100 μL of water in a 96-well plate. 1 μL (for donor samples) or 10 μL (for receiver samples) was injected for analysis.

Chromatographic separation was carried out on an Phenomenex Kinetex® C8 (100 x 2.1 mm, 2.6 μm) column at 40°C. The autosampler temperature was set at 15°C. The mobile phase consisted of gradient mixture of a) 0.1% formic acid in water and b) methanol. The flow rate was 0.4 mL/min and the run time was 2 min. MS detection was performed at positive mode using ionizing voltage of 4 kV. The interface temperature was set at 300°C and desolvation line temperature at 250°C, with ultrahigh-purity nitrogen for the drying gas (10 L/min), nebulizer gas (3 L/min) and heating gas (10 L/min). Multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) was carried out using argon as collision gas (CID), with a dwell time of 50 msec for each transition. MRM transition and CID for each analyte are shown in Table 3.

LC-MS conditions were optimized to achieve good sensitivity and chromatographic separation of analytes. The lower limits of quantification of methods are indicated in Table. Chromatograms of compounds involved in *in vitro* experiments are shown in table 2-3.

Table 2-3 MRM transitions or SIM target ions used in LC-MS/MS analysis

	Analyte	MRM* Transitions or SIM* target (m/z)	CE*	Lower Limit of quantification (as % of 50 µM)
<i>Method A</i>	Amoxicillin	366.1 -> 114.2	-20	5 nM (0.01 %)
	Nevirapine	267.2 -> 225.95	-24	5 nM (0.01 %)
	Valproic acid	143.1 (SIM)	9	1 µM (2.00 %)
	Cetirizine	389.2 -> 201.15	-39	5 nM (0.01 %)
<i>Method B</i>	Metformin	130.2 -> 60.2	-14	5 nM (0.01 %)
	Tenofovir	288.1 -> 176.1	-24	5 nM (0.01 %)
	Levetiracetam	171.2 -> 125.9	-15	20 nM (0.04 %)
	Zidovudine	268.2 -> 127.05	-11	5 nM (0.01 %)
<i>Method C</i>	Venlafaxine	278.3 -> 57.9	-17	5 nM (0.01 %)
	Tacrolimus	821.4 -> 768.3	-26	5 nM (0.01 %)
	Sertraline	306.0 -> 158.85	-18	5 nM (0.01 %)
<i>Method D</i>	Caffeine	198.09 -> 138.2	-19	5 nM (0.01 %)

* MRM: Multiple Reaction Monitoring; SIM: Selected Ion Monitoring; CE: Collision Energy.

Figure 2-1 Chromatograms of cetirizine, nevirapine, amoxicillin and valproic acid at sample level of 50 µM obtained with method A, from top to bottom respectively.

Figure 2-2 Chromatograms of tenofovir, levetiracetam, zidovudine and metformin at sample level of 50 μM obtained with method B, from top to bottom respectively.

Figure 2-3 Chromatograms of sertraline, venlafaxine and tacrolimus at sample level of 10 μM obtained with method C, from top to bottom respectively.

Figure 2-4 Chromatograms of caffeine at sample level of 1 µM obtained with method D.

2.3 *In vivo* porcine lactation model

The proposed *in vivo* model for the evaluation of drug transfer via milk to the offspring aims to enhance both IVIVE and PBPK modelling approaches. This model is also a critical tool for the preclinical testing of new compounds. In the current scientific and regulatory landscape, there is a relative lack of background data, making it challenging to fully rely on *in vitro* and *in silico* predictions. The proposed model is expected to provide quantitative data, including milk/plasma ratios along with milk and plasma concentration-time profiles, considering different phases of lactations and its underlying modifications to the milk/blood barrier.

The Consortium is fully aware of the 3Rs principles and the need to Reduce and Replace rather than increase the number of animals enrolled in preclinical trials, yet the setup of such model seems necessary given the absence of any existing, widely accepted model by health authorities for predicting or quantitating drug excretion into milk. Literature searches conducted prior to the study design confirmed that no animal *in vivo* model is currently available and capable of providing high-definition quantitative data with respect to lactation and drug transfer into milk. Furthermore, as detailed in the following sections, attention was paid to the methodological refinement of each procedure to be performed, with an overall mild severity assessment.

Within the current pharmaceutical framework, only the ICH S5 (R3) guidelines mention lactation. More specifically, section 3.5 states that “Evidence of lactational excretion can be obtained, when warranted, by sampling milk or by demonstrating exposure in offspring during the pre-weaning period”. The same document advises the use of rats for pre- and postnatal developmental (PPND) toxicity studies. Although milk collection is feasible in rats via different methods, Health Authorities do not accept quantitative data from rat milk evaluations due to the physiological differences in milk production between the rat and human. Therefore, only “presence” or “absence” of drug in rat milk can be determined, which offers limited utility for developing guidance for safe use of a drug during lactation.

Challenges associated with using rats for milk evaluations include the need for anesthesia (which could impair or bias results), the small volume of collectable samples, and the impracticality of repeating the procedure on the same female within a short timeframe. In addition to all the above, refining the procedures related to blood and milk sampling in lactating rats seems to be challenging and limited. On the other hand, performing lactation trials in non-rodents and larger animal models with well refined

procedures, could yield high resolution data, capable of describing the kinetics of the given drug (and its metabolites) in both maternal milk and plasma, and potentially in the offspring plasma, as well.

Refinement of experimental procedures was one of the primary focuses during the study design phase of the project. Given the sensitive physiological period during which the trial takes place, minimal exposure to stressors- both environmental and human-related- is crucial to ensure high levels of welfare and care, for the animals, and the generation of robust data. Therefore, the development of a novel lactation model with lactational characteristics closely mirroring those of humans is imperative for securing unique *in vivo* pharmacokinetics data. This in turn would enable better recommendations for drug labeling related to the safe use of medications during lactation. Prior to designing the *in vivo* trials to be performed within the ConcePTION project framework, an extensive literature review was carried out to select the most appropriate animal species. Based on anatomy of the mammary glands, physiology of lactation and colostrum/milk composition, the porcine species was selected as the most similar to humans. Additional considerations for model standardization and practical aspects led to the selection of Göttingen Minipigs (Ventrella et al 2021).

The first *in vivo* trial was performed using amoxicillin as test compound, a medicine widely used in porcine health management, especially during acute mastitis episodes, with well-defined background data. This pilot study was performed on both conventional hybrids and Göttingen Minipigs sows. Subsequently, three additional *in vivo* trials were performed in the same experimental facility, exclusively using Göttingen Minipigs. The trials tested metformin, levocetirizine and venlafaxine and given the scarcity of background data on these medicines in the porcine species, preliminary PK studies on juvenile pigs were performed. Samplings and procedures were kept consistent across all trials to ensure uniformity and reliability in the data collected.

To further assess the reliability and robustness of the proposed *in vivo* model, an additional amoxicillin trial, fully compliant with Good Laboratory Practice (GLP) regulations, was performed at Labcorp's Harrogate non-clinical facility. The same facility is currently performing a cassette dosing non-GLP study, simultaneously testing valaciclovir, levetiracetam, escitalopram and atenolol.

2.3.1 Pilot Amoxicillin Trial (UNIBO)

The pilot trial for Amoxicillin was performed at the University of Bologna with a total of 6 sows: three conventional hybrids and three Göttingen Minipigs. Conventional pigs were included to evaluate feasibility and perfect procedures before starting with Göttingen Minipigs sows. This choice was influenced by several factors including the experience of the research team with such breeds, the typical larger litter size and the greater volume of collectable samples.

Once the amoxicillin pilot study's preliminary assessment was completed, conventional breed sows were no longer used. Conventional pregnant sows were sourced from a local farm, SUIMAX di Massimo Ferri (Via San Michele 718, Valsamoggia 40056 BO, Italy), chosen based on the microbiological status of the facility and for the strong reproductive track records. Göttingen Minipigs pregnant sows were provided by Ellegaard Göttingen Minipigs (Soroe Landevej 302 4261 Dalmose, Denmark), which contributed as breeding facility within the project framework. All piglets included in the study were born from the above-mentioned sows in the experimental facility of the ANFI-ASA Unit, Department of Veterinary

Medical Sciences, Alma Mater Studiorum – University of Bologna (via Tolara di Sopra 50, Ozzano dell'Emilia 40064 BO, Italy).

Sows were transferred to the experimental facility one month prior to the expected delivery date, which was calculated based on the insemination/mating date and ultrasound pregnancy scan. A week before farrowing, the sows were moved to the farrowing pen. Health checks were conducted at least twice daily. Farrowing was not pharmacologically induced, due to the potential of complications, instead, it was remotely monitored by trained veterinarians.

The animals were fed a standard diet tailored to their breed: Basic Micropigs (9AB17) feed by Mucedola s.r.l. (Settimo Milanese 20019 MI, Italy), a company specialized in laboratory animal diets; while commercial sows received a formula specifically made for breeding animals, and produced by a local vendor (Molini Popolari Riuniti, Ellera-Umbertide 6019 PG, Italy). Both feeds were provided in the form of pellets, since its production process is suitable for preserving the organoleptic and hygienic characteristics of the product for up to 24 months from the date of production. Drinking water was supplied *ad libitum*, while the daily feed ratio was divided into two portions one in the early morning (7:30 AM) and one in the afternoon (3:30 PM) The total amount of feed was adjusted throughout lactation, to accommodate the significant metabolic energy expenditure of the sows.

Environmental conditions were carefully controlled. A light/dark cycle of 12/12 hours was maintained, with a minimum light intensity of 40 Lux during light hours. The temperature was set at $21 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ to meet the sows' thermal needs. With regards to the piglets, two heat lamps were installed in designated areas of the farrowing crate to maintain a temperature of $32 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$.

Piglets were individually identified with ear tags, and iron dextran (100mg) was administered IM within the first 72 hours of life.

Towards the end of the first lactation week, sows were deeply sedated by an intramuscular injection (Tiletamine/Zolazepam 3.5-5 mg/kg; Zoletil 50/50 Virbac srl) to facilitate the peripheral insertion of a long-term catheter through an auricular vein. Oxygen was provided during the procedure through a breathing mask. Throughout the entire duration of the procedure, which always lasted less than 60 min, the sows received support fluid therapy (Ringer Lactate 10 ml/kg/h) and standard anesthesia monitoring was provided including measurements of end-tidal CO₂ (ETCO₂), oxygen saturation (SpO₂), body temperature, electrocardiogram (EKG), and non-invasive blood pressure (NIBP) to ensure the well-being of the animals.

Catheterizations were performed following standard surgical sterility guidelines: the dedicated area was clipped, cleaned and disinfected; a dedicated sterile surgical environment was prepared. Surgical draping, gloves and instruments were sterilized (packed and autoclaved for each animal). The surgical field was prepped with three alternating scrubs of chlorhexidine scrubbing solution and 70% alcohol.

Seldinger's over-the-wire technique was employed for peripheral auricular vein catheterization.

The process involved:

1. Puncturing the vessel with a sharp hollow needle designed for this purpose
2. Removing the needle while leaving the plastic sheath in place to advance the guidewire through it for at least 30 mm

3. Once the wire was inserted without major resistance, removing the sheath and replacing it with a vessel dilator
4. Removing the dilator and sliding the catheter over the wire and into the vein
5. The catheter was then sutured to the skin and further secured with an IV securement dressing integrated with a chlorhexidine gluconate gel pad (Tegaderm CHG, 3M)

Heparinized saline (300IU/ml) was used as lock solution to ensure patency on a daily basis and after every blood collection. Catheter sets were purchased by Mila International:

- For Göttingen Minipigs sows; MILACATH G–idewire (SA192–) - Single Lumen - 19Ga (3.5Fr) x 25cm (10in)
- For commercial breed sows. MILACATH G–idewire (SA142–) - Single Lumen - 14Ga (6Fr) x 20cm (8in) with integrated extension set

On the first day of the trial, the sows were administered IM with 7mg/kg of amoxicillin (Clamoxyl® RTU; Pfizer) and a pharmacokinetic (PK) analysis was performed.

A total of 11 blood samples were collected:

- Before amoxicillin administration
- 30min after administration
- 60min after administration
- 90min after administration
- 2h after administration
- 3h after administration
- 4h after administration
- 5h after administration
- 6h after administration
- 12h after administration
- 24h after administration

For the remaining 3 weeks of lactation, sows were administered IM 7 mg/kg of amoxicillin once daily (SID). Injections were administered in the common preferred area for adult pigs, just behind the base of the ear, with the injection site alternated between the left and right sides each day. To minimize stress, animals were distracted and rewarded with food during the quick injection process. Sows' weights were recorded at least once a week to ensure accurate dosage adjustments of amoxicillin in accordance with their changing body weights. The trial structure, represented in figure 2-5 was as follows:

- SOW DAY: 4 matched milk/blood samples (before amoxicillin, 2, 4 and 8h after); twice a week
- SOW+PIGLET DAY: 2 matched milk/blood samples (before amoxicillin and 2h after) from the sow plus blood from 4 piglets (2 before amoxicillin and 2 piglets 30 minutes after sows' sampling); twice a week.

Figure 2-5 Schematic representation of the amoxicillin pilot lactation study in minipigs.

Blood samples from sows were carried out relatively easily due to the previously described training: animals, distracted by the food reward and accustomed to being touched on the ears, remained calm and indifferent to the operator collecting blood from the catheter. This procedure represented a significant refinement of the study methodology, as no pain was involved in this procedure.

However, it is important to note that the commercial sows occasionally showed mild aggressive behavior, as a protective response to the litter. This issue was never encountered with Göttingen Minipigs sows. Blood was collected into EDTA tubes, ensuring that the residual lock solution in the catheter lumen, along with the first milliliter of blood, was discarded to avoid contamination. Immediately after this, the catheter was flushed with saline solution and locked again with heparinized saline. The procedure was always performed by two operators: one in charge of providing the animal with the reward (usually apple juice) and the second working on the catheter. Collected blood samples were immediately centrifuged (15min, 1800rcf, 4°C) to obtain plasma, which was divided into 500µl aliquots and stored at -80°C for further analysis.

To minimize excessive stress in piglets, blood was collected from the femoral artery upon light sedation achieved with Sevoflurane, administered via breathing mask in 100% O₂. In order to ensure that the potential amoxicillin present in milk had time to be absorbed into piglets' bloodstream, the samplings were performed 30 min after maternal samplings (that always coincided with nursing). As for milk samples, the procedure was much more challenging, since the ejection period is very short in pigs and requires intense stimulation of the udder by the litter to induce oxytocin release. To facilitate precise timing for matched blood/milk collection, the research team administered exogenous oxytocin (10-20 IU, intramuscularly) to the sows. This approach ensured an efficient milk ejection reflex, enabling timely milk sampling. Milking was performed manually, as fast as possible, and directly along the length of the sow's nipple; indeed, massaging the udder does not allow good sampling results. Currently, no commercial mechanical milking devices are available for pigs. During milk collection, piglets were not separated from the sow, so operators had to compete with the litter for access to a teat. Fortunately, piglets tend to establish a preference for a particular nipple within the first lactation days and consistently aim at that one when nursing. This allowed the operators to know, in advance, where to collect milk from

each sow. Milk samples were immediately placed on ice, aliquoted as for plasma and stored at -80°C. At the end of the six trials, all samples were shipped on dry ice to BioNotus for amoxicillin quantification by validated LC-MSMS methods.

2.3.2 Metformin, Levocetirizine and Venlafaxine: preliminary PK study

Given the relative absence of background literature data on the use of metformin, venlafaxine and levocetirizine in pigs, preliminary pharmacokinetic (PK) studies were performed for each molecule at Ellegaard Göttingen Minipigs facilities in Dalmose (DK). Since the goal was to evaluate the plasma levels of the medicines after oral administration, and to comply with the 3Rs principles (Reduce, Replace, Refine), such preliminary study was done on two (n=2) juvenile, non-pregnant and non-lactating minipigs, with body weights of 14.6 and 15.5 kg. Each animal received a single dose of each medicine with a washout period of at least 96h.

The dosages to be administered were chosen by a pharmacologist within WP3, and based on existing publications for different species:

- **metformin** 125 mg (1/4 of a 500mg tablet, mixed with feed)
- **levocetirizine** 5 mg (1 tablet, mixed with feed)
- **venlafaxine** 25mg (1 tablet, mixed with feed)

Blood samples were collected from the jugular vein into K2 EDTA tubes at the following differentiated time points:

- **metformin**: before administration (0), 0.5, 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 24 hours
- **levocetirizine**: before administration (0), 0.5, 1, 2, 4, 6, 8, 24 hours
- **venlafaxine**: before administration (0), 0.25, 0.5, 1, 2, 4, 6, 24 hours

After collection, blood samples were centrifuged to separate the plasma, which was then frozen. Plasma samples were shipped on dry ice to BioNotus for quantification of the medicines with validated LC-MSMS methods. This preliminary data collection was critical for understanding the pharmacokinetics of these compounds in the Göttingen Minipigs and ensuring accurate dosing and sampling in subsequent studies.

2.3.3 Metformin trial (UNIBO)

Based on the results of the preliminary PK study performed at Ellegaard, the WP3 contributing scientists decided to administer metformin at two different dosages: a lower dose for the first 2 weeks of the trial, similar to the one used in the preliminary PKs, and a higher dose later to achieve plasma concentrations as close as possible to those observed in humans:

-
- Low dose: 500 mg/day in a single oral administration during lactation weeks 2 and 3 (low dose; 1 tablet of 500 mg)
 - High dose: 850 mg/day in a single oral administration during lactation week 4 (high dose; 1 tablet of 850 mg)

For the PK analysis performed on the first dosing day, blood sampling time points were as follows:

- Before administration (0)
- 0.5h after administration
- 1h after administration
- 2h after administration
- 3h after administration
- 4h after administration
- 6h after administration
- 8h after administration

These time points allowed for a comprehensive PK profile of metformin over an 8-hour period following administration, providing critical data for understanding its absorption and plasma concentration dynamics in lactating sows.

The rest of the study design was organized into two distinct types of trial days:

- **SOW DAYS and SOW+PIGLETS DAYS.** SOW DAY (twice a week for 3 weeks): on these days, matched blood/milk samples were collected from the sows before administration (0) and 1, 3 and 6 hours after
- **SOW+PIGLET DAY** (twice a week for 3 weeks): on these days, matched blood/milk samples were collected from the sows before administration (0) and 4 hours after, and from the piglets, blood collection was made 25 min after both maternal samplings.

2.3.4 Levocetirizine trial (UNIBO)

Based on the results of the preliminary PK study performed at Ellegaard Göttingen Minipigs, the WP3 contributing scientists decided to administer levocetirizine at two different dosages: a lower dose for the first 2 weeks of trial, similar to the one used for the preliminary PKs, and a higher dose later on to achieve plasma concentrations as close as possible to those observed in humans:

- Low dose: 15 mg/day in a single oral administration for lactation weeks 2 and 3 (low dose; 3 tablets 5mg each)
- High dose: 40 mg/day in a single oral administration for lactation week 4 (high dose; 8 tablets 5mg each)

In this specific case, the timepoints for the PK analysis performed on the first dosing day were:

- Before administration (0)
- 0.5h after administration

-
- 1h after administration
 - 2h after administration
 - 3h after administration
 - 4h after administration
 - 6h after administration
 - 8h after administration
 - 24h after administration

The rest of the study design was organized into two distinct types of trial days:

- **SOW DAYS and SOW+PIGLETS DAYS.** SOW DAY (twice a week for 3 weeks): on these days, matched blood/milk samples were collected from the sows before administration (0) and 1, 3 and 6 hours after;
- **SOW+PIGLET DAY** (twice a week for 3 weeks): on these days, matched blood/milk samples were collected from the sows before administration (0) and 4 hours after, and from the piglets, blood collection was made 25 min after both maternal samplings.

2.3.5 Venlafaxine trial (UNIBO)

Based on the results of the preliminary PK study performed at Ellegaard Göttingen Minipigs, the WP3 contributing scientists decided to administer venlafaxine at 2 different dosages: a lower one for the first 2 weeks of trial similar to the one used for the preliminary PKs, and a higher one to try and reach plasma concentrations as similar as possible to humans:

- 75 mg/day in a single oral administration for lactation weeks 2 and 3 (low dose; 1 tablet 75mg)
- 375 mg/day in a single oral administration for lactation week 4 (high dose; 5 tablets 75mg each)

In this specific case, the timepoints for the PK analysis performed on the first dosing day were:

- Before administration (0)
- 0.5h after administration
- 1h after administration
- 2h after administration
- 3h after administration
- 4h after administration
- 6h after administration
- 8h after administration

The rest of the study design was organized into two distinct types of trial days:

- **SOW DAYS and SOW+PIGLETS DAYS.** SOW DAY (twice a week for 3 weeks): on these days, matched blood/milk samples were collected from the sows before administration (0) and 1, 3 and 6 hours after.

-
- **SOW+PIGLET DAY** (twice a week for 3 weeks): on these days, matched blood/milk samples were collected from the sows before administration (0) and 4 hours after, and from the piglets, blood collection was made 25 min after both maternal samplings.

2.3.6 Amoxicillin GLP-compliant trial (LABCORP, BioNotus)

The GLP-compliant amoxicillin trial resembled the pilot study performed at UNIBO, both in terms of dosing regimen and sampling timepoints, with slight modifications.

The time points used for sows' blood collection on the first dosing day were:

- Before administration (0)
- 0.5h after administration
- 1h after administration
- 2h after administration
- 4h after administration
- 8h after administration
- 24h after administration

As opposed to the UNIBO pilot study, on this occasion milk was also collected.

The rest of the study design remained the same as described in section 2.2.1. The bioanalysis of amoxicillin samples was conducted at BioNotus with validated LC-MSMS and following GLP guidelines.

2.3.7 Cassette-dosing trial (LABCORP, BioNotus)

This trial was conducted at Labcorp, using 4 Göttingen Minipigs sows. The compounds selected to be evaluated as a cassette for this in vivo study include: valaciclovir (250 mg/day), levetiracetam (250 mg/day), escitalopram (2.5 mg/day) and atenolol (25 mg/day). A fraction of the recommended human therapeutic dose levels of all listed medications have been selected to mitigate potential toxicity and drug to drug interactions whilst still enabling the collection of meaningful results and concentrations quantifiable by LC-MS/MS-based bioanalysis method in both plasma and milk matrices.

The sampling regimen for this study was slightly modified, in order to decrease the sample days yet increasing piglets' samplings.

For the PK analysis performed on sows on the first dosing day, blood sampling time points were as follows:

- Before administration (0)
- 0.5h after administration
- 1h after administration
- 3h after administration
- 6h after administration
- 9h after administration
- 24h after administration

Milk will be also collected on the first dosing day before, 1, 3 and 6 hours after administration.

As for the rest of the trial, only “SOW+PIGLET DAYS” are kept, always twice a week for 3 weeks. On those days, maternal milk and blood samples were collected before, 1, 3 and 6 hours after administration, while matching piglets blood samples were collected with a 0.5h delay. Samples will be shipped to BioNotus for bioanalysis with validated LC-MSMS methods.

2.4 Population PK analysis

Population pharmacokinetic (PK) analysis enables studying the pharmacokinetics of a medicine at the population level using a nonlinear mixed-effects model. A population PK model consists of three main components: a structural model, a statistical model, and a covariate model (Mould and Upton., 2013).

1. The **structural model** describes the typical concentration-time profile of the modeled medicine, assuming a specific number of compartments.
2. The **statistical model** portrays the random variability (e.g., between-subject, inter-occasion, residual) of the concentration within the studied population.
3. The **covariate model** explains the variability in drug concentrations by relating it to subject-specific characteristics

By characterizing the PK of a medicine and exploring sources of variability, population PK analysis provides a comprehensive understanding of drug behavior in the studied population. Therefore, population PK analysis was added to the *in vivo* study to determine the population PK parameters and identify the source of variabilities in the lactating postpartum Göttingen Minipigs.

While the study conducted by UNIBO utilized convention pigs and Göttingen Minipigs, LABCORP’s study was conducted only in Göttingen Minipigs. Both studies obtained plasma and milk samples from the lactating sows and plasma samples from their newborn piglets. Considering that Göttingen Minipig was the chosen animal model for understanding the milk transfer of medicine (Ventrella et al., 2021), this analysis used only the data from Göttingen Minipigs. Data from Göttingen Minipigs piglets were not included in the analysis because most of the piglet plasma samples were below the lower limit of quantification. In addition, data from any animal(s) that developed disease during that period of the study were also excluded from the analysis. Additionally, subject characteristics of the sows such as bodyweight, administration site, days postpartum, offspring litter size, and study site were evaluated in population PK analysis to help explain the observed variability in drug concentration.

The population PK analysis was conducted using Monolix[®] version 2021R1 which uses the stochastic approximation expectation-maximization algorithm. A Stepwise covariate analysis was employed to identify any significant covariate effect with the following acceptance criteria:

- A decrease in Objective Function Value (OFV) of >3.84 ($p < 0.05$) and in corrected Bayes Information Criterion (cBIC) in the forward addition;
- An increase in OFV of >6.63 ($p < 0.01$) and in cBIC in the backward elimination.

Graphical evaluation of the final model was performed with the goodness-of-fit (GOF) plots and visual predictive checks (VPCs).

A virtual Göttingen Minipig population (n = 1000) was simulated with the developed model, and the median simulated amoxicillin plasma and milk profiles were utilised to calculate milk-to-plasma (M/P) ratio, daily infant dose (DID), and relative infant dose (RID) in Göttingen Minipigs using the following equations:

Milk-to-Plasma (M/P) Ratio:

$$\frac{M}{P} \text{ ratio} = \frac{AUC_{\tau, \text{milk}}}{AUC_{\tau, \text{plasma}}} \quad (\text{Equation 4})$$

Daily Infant Dosage (DID):

$$\text{Daily infant dosage} = \frac{AUC_{\tau}}{\tau} \times \text{Daily milk intake volume by a Göttingen min i pig piglet} \quad (\text{Equation 5})$$

Relative Infant Dose (RID):

$$\text{Relative infant dose} = \frac{\text{Daily infant dosage}}{\text{Maternal dosage}} \times 100\% \quad (\text{Equation 6})$$

2.5 Development of a PBPK model for lactating women

Physiology-based pharmacokinetic (PBPK) modelling is a mechanistic approach that allows to quantitatively describe the behaviour of the medicine in the body assuming the possible physiological variability and ontogeny that occurs in the individual (Kuepfer et al., 2016). PBPK modelling and simulation can be applied to simulate the pharmacokinetics of medicines in special populations, such as paediatrics, the pregnant and elderly population (Kuepfer et al., 2016; Samant et al., 2015), where for ethical reasons the voluntary and unnecessary exposure of this vulnerable population in clinical trials is avoided (Purohit, 2012). Regulatory support and acceptance for PBPK modelling has increased in recent years. One example is Veklury® (remdesivir) where PBPK modelling and simulation was used to predict exposure to medication in the paediatric population, subsequently supporting adequate dose selection for this population (CHMP, 2020).

PBPK modelling and simulation approach also carry the promise to implement a more accurate and precise prediction of medicine concentration in the human milk during the lactation phase and estimate the milk to plasma ratio of medicines excreted into human milk (Verstegen et al., 2020). The recently published lactating PBPK models typically used a whole-body PBPK model that included an additional breast compartment (Willmann et al., 2009; Abduljalil et al., 2017; Olagunju et al., 2018; Partosch et al., 2018; Garessus et al., 2019; Job et al., 2022). For modelling the transfer of chemical substances into human milk, three mechanistic concepts have been used:

(1) Direct transfer from blood (or plasma) into human milk (Byczkowski and Fisher, 1995)

-
- (2) Transfer through the uptake into the breast adipose tissue (Verner et al., 2009)
- (3) Transfer via a combination of both mechanisms (Clewell et al., 2002)

A common limitation in currently available lactation PBPK models for medicines (i.e., excluding models for chemicals) is reliance solely on the first concept (Nauwelaerts et al., 2021). Consequently, the lactation PBPK model currently under development in the ConcePTION project aims to address this by considering both the passive diffusion and the transporter-mediated transfer. The ambition is to incorporate the *in vitro* blood milk barrier transfer rates to predict the extent of medicine transferred into human milk.

Development Approach:

1. PBPK Model for an Adult Healthy Volunteer:

- Drug-related parameters (e.g., physicochemical properties) are combined with physiology-related parameters to predict the pharmacokinetic profile in adult healthy volunteer
- A training dataset of observed data in healthy volunteers is used to build the model. If necessary, parameters are estimated through the middle-out approach to fit the observed data
- The predictive performance of the model is evaluated using a second dataset (verification dataset).

2. Model verification

- The generally accepted criterion for predictive performance is less than a 2-fold misprediction (Kuepfer et al., 2016; Jones et al., 2009; Green Donna, 2018; EMA, 2018; Edginton et al, 2006; Poulin & Theil, 2009). However, a 2-fold misprediction is considered a worst-case scenario.
- Judgment should be used case-by-case for data interpretation, considering critical aspects like misprediction of a single time point in the terminal elimination phase versus misprediction of the AUC for the entire profile.

An informative tutorial on the underlying principles and generic procedures to developed and for evaluating the predictive performance of PBPK models has been published by Ezuruike et al. (2022); Kuepfer et al. (2016).

2.5.1 Lactation PBPK model

The next step was to extend the non-lactating adult PBPK models to reflect the physiology of the “lactating state”. For standardisation and feasibility reasons, PBPK models were developed and evaluated for subjects at three months postpartum. It should however be noted that the same framework can be applied for other postpartum time points. A compartment representing the lactating breasts was integrated into the PBPK model structure, with human milk represented as a sub-compartment within the breasts compartment.

Two different mechanistic concepts were considered to parametrize the transfer of medicines into human milk:

Perfusion-Limited Model:

The first model assumes rapid equilibrium between plasma and human milk. This implies that the concentration of a medicine in human milk can be calculated based on the plasma concentration and the milk-to-plasma (M/P) ratio. The M/P ratio can be calculated based on the physicochemical properties of the drug, (e.g.: pH partitioning, protein binding and distribution into milk lipid. This implies that only

the unbound and unionized molecular species will cross the blood-milk barrier. An example of this method is log-transformed phase distribution model by Atkinson & Begg (1990).

Permeability-Limited Model:

This model assumes that the local transfer rate, or biological barrier permeability, of the medicine is the rate-limiting step in the secretion process. This concept suggests that transporters or carrier proteins at the blood/milk barrier may be involved in the transfer of some medicines.

Due to limited information regarding the extent and rate of passage of medicines across the blood/milk barrier, it was decided to rely on the semi-mechanistic approach proposed by Koshimichi et al. (2011), allowing to predict *in vivo* M/P ratios based on physicochemical properties of a compound (medicine). Hence, in the lactation PBPK models, the transfer of medicines to human milk and reuptake from human milk were parametrized by the secretion (CL secretion) and reuptake (CL_reuptake) clearance, as defined by Koshimichi et al. (2011).

Secretion Clearance (CL_secretion):

(Equation 7) is calculated based on the polar surface area (PSA), molecular weight (MW) and the octanol water partition coefficient (logP) and octanol:buffer(pH 7.4) distribution coefficient (logD_{7.4}).

$$\log(\text{CL}_{\text{secretion}}) = -3.912 - 0.015 \times \text{PSA} + 3.367 \times \log(\text{MW}) - 0.164 \times \log(\text{P/D}_{7.4}) \quad (\text{Equation 7})$$

Reuptake Clearance (CL_reuptake):

(Equation 8) is calculated based on LogP and the number of hydrogen bond donors (HBD).

$$\log(\text{CL}_{\text{reuptake}}) = 2.793 + 0.179 \times \log P - 0.132 \times \text{HBD} \quad (\text{Equation 8})$$

The semi-mechanistic approach according to Koshimichi also requires knowledge of the unbound fractions of the medicines in plasma and human milk. The equations described by Atkinson and Begg (1990) were used to calculate the ('total') free fraction of the medicines in 'whole' human milk (Equation 10). This equation is based on the unbound fraction in skimmed milk (Equation 9) or the binding to milk protein, and the partition coefficient between milk lipid and ultrafiltrate (Equation 11). The unbound fraction in skimmed milk is based on the relationship between plasma protein binding and milk protein binding. The partition coefficient between milk lipid and ultrafiltrate was calculated from the octanol buffer (pH 7.4) distribution coefficient.

$$f u_{\text{skimmed milk}} = \frac{f u_p^{0.488}}{(6.94 \times 10^{-4})^{0.488} + f u_p^{0.488}} \quad (\text{Equation 9})$$

$$f u_{\text{milk, total}} = \frac{1}{\left(\frac{0.955}{f u_{\text{skimmed milk}}}\right) + 0.045 \times P_{\text{milk}}} \quad (\text{Equation 10})$$

$$P_{milk} = 10^{(-0.88+1.29 \times \text{Log}D_{7,2})} \quad (\text{Equation 11})$$

Where f_{up} : fraction unbound in plasma; $f_{u\text{skimmed milk}}$: binding to proteins in milk; P_{milk} : partitioning between milk lipid and aqueous phase; $f_{u\text{milk}}$: unbound fraction of the drug in the whole milk.

Simulations based on the lactation PBPK models were performed for a population (10 trials x 10 individuals) of lactating subjects, 3 months postpartum. The plasma and human milk concentration-time profiles were predicted. In addition, the M/P ratio (Equation 12) was calculated based on the predicted area-under-the-curve (AUC) values in plasma and milk.

$$\frac{M}{P} \text{ ratio} = \frac{AUC_{\text{human milk}}}{AUC_{\text{human plasma}}} \quad (\text{Equation 12})$$

Importantly, the data for lactation PBPK models were often missing information about the dose or the time after the last dosing. Therefore, it is recommended to evaluate the predictive performance case-by-case, in view of the availability and/or quality of the data. The evaluation of the predictive performance was mainly based on visual inspection, and whether the observed data were within the 5-95th percentile of the population prediction.

2.5.2 Lactation PBPK models with the Simcyp simulator

The PBPK models for lactation were developed using the Simcyp® simulator version 21 (Simcyp Ltd, Sheffield, UK). The Simcyp simulator features a built-in lactation module. A data collection on milk properties and physiology was performed and used for the development of the lactation module within this software platform (Abduljalil et al., 2021). The module provides two different approaches as described below, the permeability-limited and the perfusion-limited model.

Permeability-limited model:

The permeability-limited model implemented in Simcyp is a three-compartment model, consisting of extracellular, intracellular and milk compartments. This model can account for different mechanisms of medicine passage into human milk, such as passive diffusion and transporter kinetics. For passive permeability, the model includes options to allow total unbound or only unbound unionized molecules to permeate through the blood-milk barrier.

In order to adequately map the two compartments (plasma-milk) in the permeability model as described by Koshimichi et al. (2011) within the 3-compartment structure of the Simcyp lactation module, some parameters were fixed to (very) high values. To achieve this mapping, values for the passive diffusion clearance, CL_{PD} (maternal blood- milk) were fixed to a high value (Figure 2-6).

Values for secretion and reuptake clearance (CL_{re} and CL_{sec} , respectively) were calculated using R for Windows (v. 4.2.2) and Rstudio (v.2002.07.2+576) according to the equations in Koshimichi et al. (2011) (Equation 13 and 14).

Figure 2-6 Modified structure of the permeability-limited model (A) that was used to describe passage of drugs across the blood-milk barrier as part of the lactation PBPK model structure in the Simcyp simulator. The default Simcyp model is shown in panel (B).

CL_{sec} and CL_{re} were inputted in Simcyp as intrinsic clearance values. Intrinsic clearances were calculated using the well-stirred model developed by Rowland et al. (1973) (Equation 13 and 14). The fraction unbound in human milk and the total free concentration in human milk were calculated using the Atkinson & Begg equations mentioned above (Equations 9 to 11).

$$\text{Intrinsic } CL_{sec} = \frac{CL_{sec} \times Q}{f_{ublood} \times (Q - CL_{sec})} \quad (\text{Equation 13})$$

$$\text{Intrinsic } CL_{re} = \frac{CL_{re} \times Q}{f_{umilk,total} \times (Q - CL_{re})} \quad (\text{Equation 14})$$

Where f_{ublood} is the unbound fraction in blood calculated according to equation 15, $f_{umilk,total}$ is the unbound fraction of the drug in the whole milk calculated according to Equation 10, and Q is the breast tissue blood flow (this value represents ~ 3.2% of cardiac output, 9.09 L/h, as reported in Simcyp Breast&Milk tab).

$$f_{ublood} = f_{uplasma} \times \left(\frac{1}{B/P \text{ ratio}} \right) \quad (\text{Equation 15})$$

Where $f_{uplasma}$ is the unbound fraction in plasma and B/P ratio is the blood-to-plasma ratio.

Perfusion-limited model:

The perfusion-limited lactation model is based on a prediction of the M/P ratio. The module uses a combination of the Fleishaker and Atkinson & Begg models to predict M/P ratio. Alternatively, it is possible to manually set the M/P ratio or to use a user-defined script. The model assumes that there is only transfer of unbound and unionized medicines to milk, then the amount excreted depends on the milk composition, physicochemical properties of the medicine. An example of this method is the log transformed phase-distribution model by Atkinson & Begg (1990)⁸. In their model, the M/P ratio for basic drugs and acidic drugs was estimated using Equation 16 and Equation 17, respectively.

$$\ln\left(\frac{M}{P}\right) = 0.03 + 2.28 \times \ln\left(\frac{Mu}{Pu}\right) + 0.89 \times \ln f u_p + 0.51 \times \ln K \quad (\text{Equation 16})$$

$$\ln\left(\frac{M}{P}\right) = -0.41 + 9.36 \times \ln\left(\frac{Mu}{Pu}\right) - 0.69 \times \ln f u_p - 1.54 \times \ln K \quad (\text{Equation 17})$$

Where K is the milk fat to water partition coefficient and was determined according to Equation 18.

$$K = \left[\left(\frac{0.938}{f u_{\text{milk},\text{total}}} \right) + \left(1 - \frac{f_{\text{fat}}}{f u_{\text{milk},\text{total}}} + f_{\text{fat}} \times P_{\text{milk}} \right) \right] \quad (\text{Equation 18})$$

Where $f u_{\text{milk},\text{total}}$: unbound fraction of the drug in the total milk; f_{fat} : fractional volume of fat components in milk (Crt) of 0.062; $f u_p$: fraction unbound in plasma; Mu/Pu : ratio of unionized fraction of the drug in plasma to the unionized fraction of the drug in milk; P_{milk} : partitioning between milk lipid and aqueous phase defined in equation 11.

The fraction unionized in plasma and milk was calculated according to Equation 19 and 20 based on the drug's acid or basic pKa and the pH in plasma (7.4) or human milk (7.2).

$$\text{Fraction unionized (bases)} = \frac{1}{1 + 10^{(pKa - pH)}} \quad (\text{Equation 19})$$

$$\text{Fraction unionized (acid)} = \frac{1}{1 + 10^{(pH - pKa)}} \quad (\text{Equation 20})$$

Selection of transfer model across blood-milk barrier

The lactation PBPK models were established using the built-in Simcyp lactation module using either permeability-limited model or perfusion-limited model. Several properties of the models need to be considered to determine whether to assume a perfusion or permeability model in the Simcyp lactation built in module. Within the Simcyp simulator, the distribution of drugs can be described by using either a minimal or a full PBPK model. However, when using a minimal PBPK model, only the perfusion-limited model option is available (Simcyp version 21). To account for permeability, a full PBPK model can be used allowing the incorporation of uptake and efflux transporter kinetics. Considering the importance of each model, the availability of *in vitro* data and the physicochemical properties of each proposed compound, a decision tree was developed to guide the choice between perfusion- and permeability-limited models (Figure 2-7).

Once the model is selected, a virtual population was created with female subjects aged from 30 to 30.3 years old i.e., three months postpartum (geometric mean weight of 65.78kg). The simulations were performed at 10 trials with 10 individuals each, assuming a milk volume of 0.5 L and milk pH of 7.2, as reported by Koshimichi and collaborators¹². For each simulation, the administration protocol was adapted to the clinical study design reported in literature. The average (5th-95th percentile) concentration profiles in plasma and human milk were simulated. For calculating the M/P ratio, as well as the exposure, a simulation at steady state with a relatively high common dosing regimen was selected for each compound.

Based on a decision tree: amoxicillin, levetiracetam, caffeine, zidovudine, metformin, cetirizine, and tenofovir lactation PBPK models were developed assuming permeability-limited models, while perfusion-limited models were used for valproic acid, sertraline, nevirapine, and sildenafil lactation PBPK models.

Figure 2-7 Decision tree for development of lactation PBPK model within the Simcyp simulator (version 21). PBPK: Physiologically-Based Pharmacokinetic; m-PBPK: Minimal Physiologically-Based Pharmacokinetic Model; CLint: Intrinsic clearance determined (i) Utilizing the Well-Stirred Model from In Vivo Clearance Calculations Based on the Empirical Model Developed by Koshimichi or (ii) *In vitro* permeability model; Papp: Apparent Permeability Coefficient; SA: Total Surface Area of Mammary Glands; Q: Breast Blood flow of 9.09 L/h.

Infant Dose Calculation

A simulation at steady-state with a relatively high common dosing regimen (representing a worst-case scenario) was selected to calculate the PBPK model-based infant dose via breastfeeding. This approach was used to estimate only the exposure at three months postpartum, although a comparable approach can be applied to any postpartum age.

The **average concentration in human milk** ($C_{\text{ave, milk}}$) was calculated by dividing the AUC by the dosing interval.

$$C_{\text{average, milk}} = \frac{AUC_{\text{milk}}}{\tau} \quad (\text{Equation 21})$$

The **daily human milk intake in infants** at this postpartum time interval was assumed to be 150 and 200 mL/kg body weight (Food and Drug Administration, 2019).

The daily infant dosage received via breastfeeding after maternal medicine use was calculated using the average concentration in milk.

$$\text{Daily infant dosage} \left(\frac{\text{mg}}{\text{kg} \cdot \text{day}} \right) = C_{\text{average, milk}} \times \text{volume of daily milk intake} \quad (\text{Equation 22})$$

The daily infant dosage was compared with the maternal dosage for the evaluation of the relative infant dose (RID, %), as described in Equation x.

$$\text{Relative infant dose (RID, \%)} = \frac{\text{Daily infant dosage (mg/kg/day)}}{\text{Maternal dosage (mg/kg/day)}} \times 100 \quad (\text{Equation 23})$$

Where the maternal dosage is adjusted according to the maternal weight of a virtual lactating population aged between 30 to 30.3 years old, with a mean weight of 65.78 kg.

In Simcyp, the maternal weight was assumed to be the average weight of the maternal population (30 to 30.3 years old), 65.78 kg. In addition, if the drug is also used in pediatrics, the infant daily dosage via breastfeeding can also be compared to the recommended dose prescribed and administered to infants at the same age.

The development of an infant PBPK model is a critical step for accurately assessing drug exposure in infants, particularly those who are breastfed. The adult PBPK models were scaled to infants (3 months old) accounting for the physiological changes (e.g., tissue volumes, blood flow, tissue composition, blood binding, GI tract), ontogeny functions and values regarding the age dependency of anthropometrics (e.g., height and weight). The evaluation of the model follows the same criteria as for the adult PBPK model described previously. The dose per feed will be calculated from the daily infant dosage calculated from the lactation PBPK model, assuming that the infant is breastfed every 7.7 times per day (Yeung et al., 2020) and simulations at steady state will be performed.

2.6 Infant Physiology for PBPK modelling

Differences in maturational physiology of breastfed infants have been described in multiple articles, such as a different pattern of growth, weight and body composition, compared to formula-fed infants. However, due the fragmented data, their integration and comprehensive analysis is limited (Blake et al 2006); Bonner et al 2015). Although the insight into pharmacokinetics and physiologically based modelling is evolving, there is still limited knowledge regarding the physiology of special populations, such as breastfed infants (Smits et al 2019).

To address this gap, a novel dataset on the physiology of breastfed infants is being generated by conducting a semi-systematic literature review. The aim is to generate a virtual population for PBPK models of breastfed infants, which will enable more accurate simulations and predictions of drug exposure in this specific population.

First, a detailed search strategy was carried out using PubMed, Embase, Cochrane and Web of Science databases with terms relating to infants, breastfeeding and pharmacokinetics. The results of these databases (5663, 5999, 1000 and 3108, respectively) have been screened for inclusion, e.g., exclusive breastfeeding for at least 4 months, and exclusion criteria, e.g., preterm infants. After the screening of the results, 223 articles have been included for the generation of a new data set. Next, data on 13 categories relating to pharmacokinetics were assessed: growth, intake, body composition, blood composition, oral absorption, gastrointestinal (GI) transit time, GI fluids, renal function, blood flow and organ volumes. Finally, the new data set can be imported into multiple PBPK platforms (Simcyp and PKSim) as a virtual population and be compared with the present physiological input of the neonatal PBPK template in developed PBPK models. This observation will determine the benefit and significance of the new data set on the maturational physiology of breastfed infants in PBPK software.

Efforts to develop an infant PBPK model are ongoing. The reference PBPK model developed for adults was scaled to infants (3 months old) accounting for the physiological changes (e.g., tissue volumes, blood flow, tissue composition, blood binding, GI tract), ontogeny functions and values regarding the age dependency of anthropometrics (e.g., height and weight). The evaluation of the model followed the same criteria as for the reference PBPK model described previously. The dose per feed for breastfed infants was calculated based on the daily infant dosage derived from the lactation PBPK model, under the assumption that the infant is breastfed every 4 hours. Simulations at steady state were performed to ensure accurate and consistent exposure estimates.

3 Results

The first data package includes a comprehensive dataset of information for multiple compounds across various models (*in vitro*, *in vivo*, and PBPK).

The dataset for amoxicillin across all models (*in vitro*, *in vivo* and PBPK model) is provided, while *in vivo* results for levocetirizine, metformin, and venlafaxine, as well as PBPK modelling and *in vitro* data for ten compounds, are available.

3.1 *In vitro* models representative of the blood milk barrier

The first step involved establishing culture protocols for both human primary cells (hMECs) and cell lines, including MCF-7, MCF-10A and PMC42-LA (La Mantia et al 2024). For the mpMECs, a protocol for their isolation and culture were also established (Bernardini et al 2024). Detailed information about these protocols can be found in D3.3 from the IMI ConcePTION project.

An *in vitro* model was developed to measure bidirectional permeability coefficients across the blood-milk barrier. This model aims to achieve a combination between experimental simplicity (feasibility) with predictive potential. This approach is similar to the well-established method that uses Caco-2 cells to calculate the permeability of medicines. The *in vitro* model does not investigate metabolism at the blood-milk barrier, (as indicated by the EMA experts during the meeting in March 2023, but this appears to be in line with the limited metabolism at the blood-milk barrier. In fact, no evidence for the expression of metabolizing enzymes at the blood-milk barrier (except for esterases present in human milk) was found.

Following that step, the characterization of the human *in vitro* models was performed:

Monolayer integrity

Cell lines (D3.3):

- PMC42-LA did not form a tight cellular layer
- MCF-10A did not form a tight cellular layer
- MCF-7 initially formed a tight barrier but could not be reproduced at a later stage. This might be due to a disadvantage of cell lines, namely genetic drift (Nugoli et al., 2003).

Primary cells (hMECs):

- Trypsin treatment + hormonal stimulation: The use of hMECs has first been described by Kimura et al. (2006). They obtained a tight cellular barrier using 3 trypsin treatments in combination with hormonal stimulation, resulting in a differentiated *in vitro* model. Unfortunately, attempts to reproduce this method did not result in a tight barrier in our hands. Further research beyond ConcePTION may explore different strategies for achieving an active lactation system and to evaluate the impact (as requested by EMA experts during the meeting in March 2023) in respect to transport across the blood-milk barrier
- 10 % Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS): We were able to form a tight barrier with hMECs with addition of 10 % FBS (Fetal Bovine Serum) to the culture medium after seeding the cells on the inserts.

A tight monolayer was obtained after +/- 35 days, with some variability in the maximal values that are reached.

Figure 3-1 Transepithelial Electrical Resistance (TEER) and sodium fluorescein (marker for paracellular pathway ‘leakage’) transport across human mammary epithelial cells cultured for up to 47 days. Thirty-five days of culture were considered adequate to obtain a monolayer suitable for transport experiments with medicines, allowing determination of permeability coefficients across the blood-milk barrier.

None of the selected cell lines offered a good *in vitro* model since they did not form a tight monolayer. In contrast, the primary mammary epithelial cells performed well in culture and are also the most biorelevant model. Thus, primary cells form the preferred starting point for an *in vitro* model representative for medicine transfer across the human blood-milk barrier. Therefore, further characterization was only performed for the hMECs and mpMECs. A comparison was made with permeability coefficients across the most widely used epithelial *in vitro* models (as requested by EMA experts), Caco-2 cells. Such an approach was recently also done for P-gp substrates. However, it was found that using Caco-2 cells as a surrogate model to predict drug excretion into human milk would lead to an overprediction of the M/P ratio (Zhang et al., 2022).

Epithelial morphology

The primary human mammary epithelial cells were selected as the preferred *in vitro* model. Given that the required culture time of 35 days is relatively long, immunocytochemistry with confocal microscopy was performed to confirm that the cells retain their desired epithelial phenotype after such a long culture time on Transwell™ inserts. The cells showed the expression of epithelial markers (Figure 3-2).

Figure 3-2 Epithelial markers confirm stability of epithelial cell type after 35 days in HMECS

Tight junctions

The presence of tight junctions in the *in vitro* model was shown after 35 days of culture on the Transwell™ inserts (Figure 3-1). This confirms that a tight barrier is indeed formed by the hMECs (Figure 3-3).

Figure 3-3 Staining for tight junction proteins ZO-1 and Occludin in hMECs.

Figure 3-5 hMEC permeability coefficients for probe substrates of transporter function.

Primary minipig cells (mpMECs)

The mammary epithelial cells from Göttingen minipigs (mpMECs) were selected as a promising animal *in vitro* model that can assist in extrapolating *in vitro* and *in vivo* minipig data to *in vivo* human predictions, possibly in combination with PBPK modelling. Furthermore, this approach aims to the establishment of a correlation between hMECs and mpMECs in terms of transport of medicines across the blood-milk barrier. This correlation provided further insights, suggesting that mpMECs could serve as a surrogate for hMECs. A potential advantage of mpMECs is their shorter culture time, but transport experiments might be complicated with the fact that the barrier is not as tight as observed in human cells. mpMECs were isolated, characterized and expanded as previously described for hybrid commercial pig (Bernardini et al., 2021). Three primary cell lines were produced and utilized for barrier study. To avoid single animal variability a cellular pool of the three lines was performed.

Figure 3-6 Staining of tight junctions with ZO1 and Occludin, and the monolayer integrity results for mpMECs in pool.

The mpMECs formed a compact monolayer expressing tight junction proteins ZO-1 and Occludin. Trans-epithelial electrical resistance (TEER) measurements and sodium fluorescein transport assays confirmed the mpMECs barrier formation after four days of culture time on transwell inserts. (Figure 3-6), which is considerably faster than human cells, and could be beneficial (Point 2, Section 1.7). Despite this, the monolayer integrity results indicate that hMECs create a significantly tighter barrier compared to mpMECs, as evidenced by their higher TEER values and lower sodium fluorescein transport rates. The relative TEER Variability is comparable between hMECs and mpMECs. The intra-experiment coefficient of variation (CV) ranges from 15 % to 32 % for hMECs and 17% to 28 % for mpMECs, while the inter-experiment CV for hMECs and mpMECs, is 24% and 17%, respectively.

Expression of membrane transporters

In the swine species, a customized array (RT2 ProfilerTM PCR Array Pig Drug Transporters, Cod PASS-070Z, Qiagen) was utilised to evaluate the transcriptional profile of drug transporters in mpMECs. The transcriptional profile of mpMEC drug transporters showed a different level of gene expression, ranging from ΔCt values that were very negative (lower expression) to ΔCt values that were less negative (higher expression). Only two genes, SLC22A3 and SLC22A8, were not detectable (Figure 3-7).

The results from the *in vitro* experiments with probe substrates demonstrated that both hMECs and mpMECs *in vitro* models are capable of distinguishing between paracellular and transcellular transport. However, TEER values in mpMECs were significantly lower to hMECs. It is recommended to exclude transwell inserts with a TEER value below 35 from the experiments, as it was observed that these were associated with significantly higher apparent permeability.

Overall, the apparent permeability of mpMECs was slightly higher compared to hMECs, which aligns with the TEER results. Additionally, the probe substrates for transporters showed no polarity in either of the probe substrates, suggesting that the activity of these transporters is either non-existent or minimally impactful in mpMECs.

The integration of data from these *in vitro* models, along with the *in vivo* studies that are currently ongoing in ConcePTION WP3 for Göttingen Minipig and WP4 for humans will facilitate the development of *in vitro* / *in vivo* extrapolation algorithms, which could predict the passage of compounds across the blood/milk barrier.

Data Interpretation and Calibration

In terms of data obtained from independent experiments, inter-experiment variability in transepithelial transport remained relatively limited, with a coefficient of variation (CV) of 28 % for hMECs and 25 % for mpMECs. This is notable given the sometimes-pronounced differences in TEER values. Nevertheless, it is recommended to calibrate transport data between different experiments, for instance by using reference compounds. These compounds should be repeated in every experiment aimed at determining permeability coefficients for novel compounds. Such an approach is typically used for transepithelial transport experiments, such as those performed using Caco-2 monolayers.

Polarity and Passive Transport Mechanisms

For many of the selected medicines, there was no clear polarity in transport across the blood-milk barrier, with transport rates comparable in both directions. This suggests a minimal impact of (saturated) active transport mechanisms mediated by membrane transporters, which are known to mediate cellular uptake and efflux of xenobiotics, including medicines. For the medicines without clear polarity in transport, the permeability across the blood-milk barrier is mainly driven by passive mechanisms and can be predicted based on physicochemical properties, such as lipophilicity, pKa values, molecular weight and protein binding. The highest polarity in transport was observed for sertraline, which could potentially indicate transporter involvement. Sertraline is known as a high affinity substrate for P-glycoprotein (P-gp). However, P-gp is not expected to play an important role in the blood-milk barrier, a conclusion that was also confirmed previously in the *in vitro* models using fexofenadine as a probe substrate.

Correlation Analysis Between *In Vitro* and *In Vivo* Models

Linear regression was performed to determine whether the *in vitro* hMECs model correlates with the *in vivo* milk-plasma (M/P) ratio. It was found that neither the efflux ratio (ER) nor the apparent permeability in the apical-to-basolateral direction ($P_{app, AB}$) correlate with the *in vivo* M/P ratio in humans. However, a significant correlation was observed between $P_{app, BA}$ in hMECs (indicating secretion towards human milk) and the M/P ratio after logarithmic transformation. Although there is still some unexplained variation, most likely due to factors related to unionized fraction or protein binding.

Figure 3-9 Correlation of *in vitro* basolateral-to-apical permeability (Papp, BA) in human mammary epithelial cells (hMECs) and unionized fractions in human plasma (Fni7.4) and milk (Fni7.0) with in vivo milk-to-plasma ratio (M/P ratio)

Dotted line represents the linear regression line for Papp, BA (10^{-6} cm/s) in hMECs (A) or the ratio of Fni7.4 and Fni7.0 (B) with the in M/P ratio, based on the median log-transformed values for the model medicines and probes substrates shown as individual points. hMECs were grown on PET transwell inserts with a pore size of $0.4 \mu\text{m}$ and a surface area of 0.3 cm^2 at a density of $3.3 \cdot 10^5$ cells/ cm^2 in full growth medium with 10 % fetal bovine serum. Papp, BA of amoxicillin was fixed at the permeability coefficient ($0.05 \cdot 10^{-6}$ cm/s) calculated from the quantification limit. In vivo human M/P ratios were taken from literature.

To evaluate whether primary Göttingen minipig mammary epithelial cell model (mpMECs) could serve as a surrogate model for human mammary epithelial cells (hMECs), the correlation of ER and Papp between both models was evaluated. Significant correlations were found between the ER and Papp values, when comparing the *in vitro* results from both models (Figure 3-10).

For permeabilities obtained from the Caco-2 model as reported in literature, a logarithmic transformation of data revealed significant correlation for both BA and AB permeabilities, but no significant correlation was found for ER with the hMECs *in vitro* model (Figure 3-11).

Figure 3-11 Correlation of *in vitro* permeability (10-6 cm/s) in human mammary epithelial cells (hMECs) and Caco-2 cell line

Dotted line represents the linear regression line for Papp, BA (A) or Papp, AB (B) in hMECs and Caco-2 cell line, based on the median log-transformed values for the model medicines and probes substrates shown as individual points. hMECs were grown on PET transwell inserts with a pore size of 0.4 μm and a surface area of 0.3 cm^2 at a density of $3.3 \cdot 10^5$ cells/ cm^2 for hMECs in full growth medium with 10 % fetal bovine serum. Papp, AB of amoxicillin, methotrexate, sulfasalazine, tenofovir and zidovudine was fixed at the permeability coefficient ($0.11 \cdot 10^{-6}$ cm/s) calculated from the quantification limit in hMECs. Papp, BA of amoxicillin was fixed at the permeability coefficient ($0.05 \cdot 10^{-6}$ cm/s) calculated from the quantification limit in hMECs. Caco-2 efflux ratios were taken from literature.

Potential Limitations and Suggested Strategies

One of the primary limitations for testing additional medicines in the *in vitro* models involves potential issues related to cytotoxicity or insolubility. However, these challenges could be mitigated by using similar strategies to those used in Caco-2 experiments. The presence of FBS or organic solvent can help reduce nonspecific binding (e.g. to plastic in the *in vitro* system). Biorelevant solving systems and buffers including protein could enhance the solubility of medicines. To increase biorelevance, exploratory experiments were performed using FBS (to mimic plasma binding) and 10% human milk. These conditions were intended to naturally account for protein binding. The results showed a significant correlation between the permeabilities obtained in the *in vitro* model without human milk and those obtained in the presence of human milk, explaining about 80% of the variation.

Figure 3-12 hMEC permeability coefficients for model medicines

Figure 3-13 mpMEC permeability coefficients for model medicines.

Figure 3-14

3.2 *In vivo* porcine lactation model

The trial setup allowed easy and consistent access to the ear catheter for blood collection and the mammary glands for milk collection. Despite being in the vulnerable post-partum period, the sows remained cooperative throughout, even when piglets were temporarily removed for blood sampling.

3.2.1 Amoxicillin trial (UNIBO)

During the initial dosing and pharmacokinetic (PK) samplings, one of the Göttingen Minipigs sows (ID: I20) exhibited severe lethargy and hyperthermia. The animal was immediately treated with NSAIDs (Flunixin Meglumine, 2.2mg/kg) IV fluid therapy (Lactated Ringer, 5 ml/kg/h) and imaging revealed a severe gastric dilation. Consequently, a gastric washing under general anesthesia (Proposure® 4mg/Kg) was performed. The sow fully recovered within 24 hours and maintained nursing without interruption. However, to prevent potential bias to the trial outcomes, the affected sow was withdrawn from the trial for a week and reintroduced during the third lactation week (P15, at the third lactation week). Nonetheless, the amoxicillin administration continued as planned to ensure consistency in samplings across animals.

The results of the bioanalytical assays performed to quantify amoxicillin in both plasma and milk along with the analyses validation and methodology can be found in Bionotus report from Armoudjian Y. and Lin Q. The lower limit of quantification (LLOQ) was 10 ng/mL, and the upper (ULOQ) 10000 ng/mL. The comprehensive dataset has been deposited into the Institutional Research Data Repository of the University of Bologna (<https://doi.org/10.6092/unibo/amsacta/7429>).

The following tables and graphs represent the averaged data of both conventional and Gottingen Minipigs sows, as no significant differences were recorded between breeds (Table 3-1, Table 3-2). Generally, amoxicillin concentrations were consistently above the quantification limits in sows' plasma and milk, with the expected exception of the initial plasma sample (collected before the first amoxicillin dosing). This finding confirms that amoxicillin is consistently able to cross the blood/mammary barrier into milk.

The PK analyses performed on sows on the first dosing day are listed in Figure 3-15 (data from I20 were excluded due to complications during the PK Day, as described above). At T_{max}, the mean plasma amoxicillin concentration was 1.44 µg/ml. Amoxicillin was also at quantifiable levels in plasma, 24h after dosing, although in very low concentrations (mean 0.097 µg/ml).

Figure 3-15 Plasma PK of amoxicillin (7mg/kg IM, SID) in conventional and Göttingen Minipigs sows on the first day of dosing. Histograms represent the mean value.

Descriptive statistics for the quantification of amoxicillin into maternal plasma and milk samples are reported in Table 3-1 and Table 3-2 respectively.

Table 3-1 Amoxicillin quantification (µg/mL) in maternal plasma samples. n indicates the number of samples

	n	Min µg/mL	Max µg/mL	Mean µg/mL	SEM µg/mL
Before administration	65	0.014	1.849	0.295	0.034
2h after administration	65	0.274	4.977	1.351	0.090
4h after administration	34	0.259	2.349	0.998	0.074
8h after administration	32	0.218	1.726	0.785	0.058

Table 3-2 Amoxicillin quantification ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) in maternal milk samples. n indicates the number of samples.

	n	Min $\mu\text{g/mL}$	Max $\mu\text{g/mL}$	Mean $\mu\text{g/mL}$	SEM $\mu\text{g/mL}$
Before administration	56	0.012	2.039	0.125	0.037
• 2h after administration	65	0.014	1.607	0.217	0.037
• 4h after administration	32	0.010	2.583	0.290	0.083
• 8h after administration	31	0.026	0.390	0.153	0.019

When analyzing the amoxicillin concentrations in sows' matched blood/milk samples collected before administration and at 2, 4 and 8 hours after, distinct trends were observed between the two matrices. Indeed, the highest plasma concentrations were recorded 2 hours after IM amoxicillin administration, while the highest milk concentrations were 4 hours after. For plasma, all experimental time points had statistically significant differences between each other (Kruskal-Wallis test, Conover post-hoc test; $p < 0.0001$); as for milk, all the time points after administration statistically differed from the pre-administration level (Kruskal-Wallis test, Conover post-hoc test; $p < 0.0001$), but not between the post-administration time points themselves.

The results of the statistical evaluations are indicated by different letters in Figure 3-16.

Figure 3-16 Amoxicillin concentrations ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) in sows' plasma and milk samples at the four experimental time points. Different letters indicate statistically relevant differences ($p < 0.05$). Histograms represent the mean; error bars represent the SEM (standard error mean)

Out of the 136 blood samples collected from piglets, only 9 showed amoxicillin levels above the quantification limits (LLOQ 10 ng/ml, ULOQ 10000 ng/ml): five were collected before maternal dosing and four 2h afterwards (Figure 3-17). Thus, no inferential statistical evaluation was performed.

Figure 3-17 Scatter plot of the individual values of amoxicillin ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) recorded into piglets plasma. LLOQ: $10\text{ng}/\text{ml}$; ULOQ: $10000\text{ng}/\text{ml}$.

Nonetheless, when comparing the milk samples collected 2 hours after amoxicillin administration and the corresponding piglets' plasma, the difference seems to suggest that, at this time point, piglet exposure to medicine in milk is low and not detectable with the developed method (Figure 3-18). It is important to highlight that piglet's plasma was collected 30 min after milk sampling to allow potential absorption in the bloodstream, and there is a chance that the selected timepoint may have impaired drug detection.

Figure 3-18 Amoxicillin levels in sows' milk and piglets' plasma collected 2h after maternal dosing. Histograms represent the mean; error bars represent the SEM (standard error mean)

The aim of this first lactation study was to assess if the swine species, selected upon extensive literature review, could effectively be used to build an *in vivo* lactation model able to provide quantitative and translatable data. Additionally, this preliminary study was necessary to assess the feasibility of the procedures, given the limited data available on milk collection in pigs. Pigs are relatively easy to train and get accustomed to human interaction in a short amount of time when the correct training procedures

are applied; accordingly, sows were successfully clicker-trained with a food reward to be approached and touched on the ears (for blood sampling) and the abdominal region (for milk collection). The main refinement to the experimental procedures, along with the above-mentioned training, was the placement of a peripherally inserted central venous catheter (from an auricular vein) for repeated blood sampling. This allowed the researchers to collect blood samples without inflicting any pain to the sows, while a second operator distracted them with a food reward. When looking at piglets' samplings, catheter placement was not feasible due to their size, but blood was collected under deep sedation achieved by Sevoflurane administered through a breathing mask.

Overall, the study design used for this preliminary amoxicillin trial effectively highlighted both the advantages and areas of improvement in using this new *in vivo* platform to investigate infant medicine exposure through milk. The procedures were feasible and well tolerated by the animals, who gained confidence and trust during the preliminary training sessions.

Maternally administered amoxicillin reached quantifiable levels in Gottingen minipig milk, while systemic plasma levels in piglets were very low, and frequently below the quantification limit of the bioanalysis method. This proof-of-concept study illustrates the unique value of the minipig for *in vivo* lactation studies including exposure monitoring in off-spring.

3.2.2 Metformin, Levocetirizine and Venlafaxine: preliminary PK study

The preliminary PK study allowed the consortium to understand what dose/doses to test in the following trials, since species-specific literature was poor or completely lacking. Animals well tolerated the administered medicines and completed the study without noticeable side effect. The results of the metformin preliminary PK study (dose: 125mg) are reported in Table 3-3 and represented in Figure 3-19.

Table 3-3 Quantified concentrations of metformin in Gottingen Minipigs juvenile animals (n=2)

Timepoint (h)	METFORMIN	
	Animal 1 (ng/mL)	Animal 2 (ng/mL)
0	0.000	0.000
0.5	224.652	729.120
1	455.367	816.716
2	436.592	695.641
3	311.452	435.826
4	198.767	265.642
6	70.257	112.794
24	17.177	15.473

Figure 3-19 Preliminary metformin PK study on juvenile Gottingen Minipigs (n=2). Administered dose: 125mg, oral administration.

The results of the levocetirizine preliminary PK study (dose: 5mg) are reported in Table 3-4 and represented in Figure 3-20.

Table 3-4 Quantified concentrations of levocetirizine in Gottingen Minipigs juvenile animals (n=2)

Timepoint (h)	LEVOCETIRIZINE	
	Animal 1 (ng/mL)	Animal 2 (ng/mL)
0	0.000	0.000
0.25	70.158	207.899
0.5	105.068	210.451
1	139.449	183.042
2	168.685	174.640
4	122.919	123.146
24	6.175	5.941

Figure 3-20 Preliminary levocetirizine PK study on juvenile Gottingen Minipigs (n=2). Administered dose: 5mg, oral administration.

The results of the venlafaxine preliminary PK study (dose: 25mg) are reported in Table 3-5 and represented in Figure 3-21. In this case, also its main metabolite O-desmethyl venlafaxine was quantified.

Table 3-5 Quantified concentrations of venlafaxine and O-desmethyl venlafaxine in Gottingen Minipigs juvenile animals (n=2)

Timepoint (h)	VENLAFAXINE		O-DESMETHYL VENLAFAXINE	
	Animal 1 (ng/mL)	Animal 2 (ng/mL)	Animal 1 (ng/mL)	Animal 2 (ng/mL)
0	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
0.5	24.834	16.203	5.652	16.399
1	23.325	16.379	8.270	18.053
2	7.695	10.888	11.179	14.289
4	1.824	4.349	11.654	20.582
6	0.000	2.298	13.924	20.096
8	2.010	2.407	18.364	17.278
24	0.000	1.859	3.101	9.082

Figure 3-21 Preliminary venlafaxine PK study on juvenile Gottingen Minipigs (n=2). Administered dose: 25mg, oral administration.

3.2.3 Metformin trial (UNIBO)

The full dataset containing the results of the UNIBO metformin trial are currently deposited in the Research Data Repository of the University of Bologna with an embargo of 8 months (<https://doi.org/10.6092/unibo/amsacta/7430>). Metformin was quantifiable in all maternal samples, except those collected before the first dosing, as anticipated. The determination range of Metformin in the samples was between 2 ng/mL and 1600 ng/mL.

The results of the plasmatic PK study performed on sows on the first day of metformin dosing (low dose, 500 mg/day) are represented in Figure 3-22.

Figure 3-22 Quantification of metformin in sow's plasma upon first dosing (low dose, 500 mg/day). The graph represents the mean value; error bars indicate the standard error of the mean (SEM)

Descriptive statistics for the quantification of metformin into maternal plasma and milk samples are reported in Table 3.6 and 3.7 respectively.

Table 3-6 Metformin quantification (ng/ml) in maternal plasma samples. Low dose was administered for 2 weeks, the high one for 1 week.

		<i>n</i>	Min ng/ml	Max ng/ml	Mean ng/ml	SEM ng/ml
Low dose 500 mg/day	Pre-metformin	27	0	509.5	58.89	18.57
	1h post	13	225.9	3032	1423	215.8
	3h post	13	411.3	2156	1248	148.4
	4h post	13	429.5	1792	1075	131.4
	6h post	14	67.18	939.6	487.2	68.01
High dose 850 mg/day	Pre-metformin	11	39.74	193.4	107.4	15.62
	1h post	5	133.7	3090	1393	561.7
	3h post	6	106.9	2484	1032	434.7
	4h post	5	361.8	3087	1372	544.3
	6h post	6	118.8	1145	656.2	180.3

Table 3-7 Metformin quantification (ng/ml) in maternal milk samples. Low dose was administered for 2 weeks, the high one for 1 week.

		<i>n</i>	Min ng/ml	Max ng/ml	Mean ng/ml	SEM ng/ml
Low dose 500 mg/day	Pre-metformin	29	0	290.5	139.1	14.69
	1h post	14	41.42	581	206.4	36.01
	3h post	14	263.3	1090	523.9	72.00
	4h post	15	149.4	1319	579.3	100.5
	6h post	14	169.4	1041	490.8	63.48
High dose 850 mg/day	Pre-metformin	16	103	468.8	267.9	28.44
	1h post	8	164.1	629.2	331.5	52.87
	3h post	8	162.5	596	403.9	50.77
	4h post	8	171.5	1050	432.4	97.39
	6h post	8	272.3	1187	518.2	106.8

Figure 3-23 represents the trends of the concentrations of metformin in maternal plasma with data presented both separately for each dose and combined. The first two panels also include results of the statistical analysis (Kruskal-Wallis test followed by multiple comparisons post-hoc test) aimed to identify differences between timepoints within the same dosing regimen.

For both administered dosages, the peak plasma concentration of metformin was recorded 1-hour post-administration, with a statistically relevant difference in comparison to the pre-metformin timepoint.

Looking at the high dosage, it can be noticed how the intermediate point (3 hours administration) seems to not follow the gradual descending trend of the medicine, probably due to the relatively low sample size.

Figure 3-23 Graphical representation of the concentrations of metformin in sows' plasma upon oral administration. The first two panels are divided per dose and report statistical differences (different letters indicate differences between timepoints, $p < 0.05$); the last panel shows all plasma data combined.

Accordingly, Figure 3-24 shows the results of the quantification in milk, with the same approach described above for plasma. In this case, the highest metformin concentration was recorded 4 hours after administration of the low dose, and 6 hours after administration of the high one.

Figure 3-24 Graphical representation of the concentrations of metformin in sows' milk upon oral administration. The first two panels are divided per dose and report statistical differences (different letters indicate differences between timepoints, $p < 0.05$); the last panel shows all milk data combined.

As for piglets' plasma, metformin was quantifiable in 43 out of 64 samples. No statistical differences were recorded upon comparison between samples collected before maternal administration and those collected 4 hours post-maternal administration. This aligns with the study design, wherein the sows were continually dosed from the first up to the last day of trial. Therefore, the medicine levels detected in piglets blood collected before the daily maternal administration reflect the fact that, after first dosing, milk always shows a certain medicine quantity.

Figure 3-25 shows the metformin level in piglets' plasma at both timepoints, divided by maternal dosing regimens (low dose 500 mg/day; high dose 850 mg/day) and also the comparison with the pertinent

maternal milk levels. Despite metformin being present in the majority of piglets' samples, its levels are extremely low when compared to the one quantified in the corresponding maternal milk.

Figure 3-25 Metformin levels in piglets' plasma collected before and 4h after maternal administration and comparison with corresponding milk levels.

3.2.4 Levocetirizine trial (UNIBO)

The full dataset containing the results of the UNIBO levocetirizine trial are currently deposited in the Research Data Repository of the University of Bologna with an embargo of 8 months (<https://doi.org/10.6092/unibo/amsacta/7430>).

Out of the 4 pregnant sows shipped for the levocetirizine trial, one delivered non-vital piglets 8 days before the anticipated farrowing date. This trial was therefore carried out with 3 sows and 3 litters.

Levocetirizine was quantifiable in all maternal samples, aside from the ones collected before the first dosing, which is consistent with expectations. The determination ranges of levocetirizine were between 1 ng/mL and 1000 ng/mL. The results of the plasmatic PK study performed on the sows on the first day of levocetirizine dosing (low dose, 15 mg/day) are represented in Figure 3-26.

Figure 3-26 Quantification of levocetirizine in sow's plasma upon first dosing (low dose, 15 mg/day). The graph represents the mean value; error bars indicate the standard error of the mean (SEM).

Descriptive statistics for the quantification of levocetirizine into maternal plasma and milk samples are summarised in Table 3.8 and 3.9, respectively. During this trial, two vascular catheters lost patency right before the passage to the higher dose, therefore the number of plasmatic samples in this case was reduced (Table 3.8), and was included in the descriptive statistics but not into the inferential one. Nonetheless, the animals continued the trial, received the highest dosage and milk was still collected.

Table 3-8 Levocetirizine quantification (ng/ml) in maternal plasma samples. Low dose was administered for 2 weeks, the high one for 1 week.

		<i>n</i>	Min ng/ml	Max ng/ml	Mean ng/ml	SEM ng/ml
Low dose 15 mg/day	Pre-levocetirizine	19	15.26	183.8	65.46	10.16
	1h post	9	92.57	376.6	181.3	30.3
	3h post	10	71.95	454.9	279.1	41.51
	4h post	9	97.55	613.5	336.4	62.03
	6h post	10	49.1	577.3	238	46.2
High dose 40 mg/day	Pre-levocetirizine	3	30.32	102.4	63.86	20.95
	1h post	1	112.1	112.1	112.1	/
	3h post	1	116.5	116.5	116.5	/
	4h post	0	/	/	/	/
	6h post	1	106.1	106.1	106.1	/

Table 3-9 Levocetirizine quantification (ng/ml) in maternal milk samples. Low dose was administered for 2 weeks, the high one for 1 week.

		<i>n</i>	Min ng/ml	Max ng/ml	Mean ng/ml	SEM ng/ml
Low dose 15 mg/day	Pre-levocetirizine	25	0	185.6	33.25	8.621
	1h post	11	20.68	141.7	58.47	10.47
	3h post	12	29.29	156.3	74.6	10.26
	4h post	11	29.01	145.6	76.94	10.92
	6h post	12	22.99	100.6	52.84	7.354
High dose 40 mg/day	Pre-levocetirizine	7	21.29	414.3	146.1	55.59
	1h post	3	36.24	269.2	179.5	72.39
	3h post	3	27.99	356.5	220.4	98.91
	4h post	2	281.9	511.6	396.8	114.9
	6h post	3	31.29	364.2	223.8	99.58

Figure 3-27 represents the trends of the concentrations of levocetirizine in maternal plasma, only for the low dosing regimen; the results of the statistical analysis (Kruskal-Wallis test followed by the multiple comparisons post-hoc test) performed to assess differences between timepoints are also included. The plasmatic peak was recorded 4 hours after administration, with all timepoints being statistically different when compared to the pre-levocetirizine one.

Figure 3-27 Graphical representation of the concentrations of levocetirizine in sows' plasma upon oral administration (different letters indicate differences between timepoints, $p < 0.05$).

Figure 3-28 shows the results of the quantification of levocetirizine in milk, firstly data divided per dose and then together. The first two panels also report the results of the statistical analysis (Kruskal-Wallis test followed by the multiple comparisons post-hoc test) performed to assess differences between timepoints within the same dosing regimen. In both cases, the highest levocetirizine concentration were

recorded 4 hours after administration of both doses, with a more marked increase in the higher dose (despite the lack of statistical difference, most likely due to the poor sample size).

Figure 3-28 Graphical representation of the concentrations of levocetirizine in sows' milk upon oral administration. The first two panels are divided per dose and report statistical differences (different letters indicate differences between timepoints, $p < 0.05$); the last panel shows all milk data combined.

As for piglets' plasma, levocetirizine was quantifiable in 45 out of 51 samples. No statistical differences were recorded upon comparison between samples collected before maternal administration and the ones collected 4h post-maternal administration. Figure 3-29 shows the levocetirizine level in piglets' plasma at both timepoints, divided per maternal dosing (low dose 15 mg/day; high dose 40 mg/day) and the comparison with the pertinent maternal milk levels. Despite levocetirizine being present in most piglets' samples, its levels are extremely low when compared to the one quantified in the corresponding maternal milk.

Figure 3-29 Levocetirizine levels in piglets' plasma collected before and 4h after maternal administration and comparison with corresponding milk levels.

3.2.5 Venlafaxine trial (UNIBO)

The full dataset containing the results of the UNIBO venlafaxine trial are currently deposited in the Research Data Repository of the University of Bologna with an embargo of 8 months (<https://doi.org/10.6092/unibo/amsacta/7430>).

For the venlafaxine study, it was decided to quantify both venlafaxine and its main metabolite O-desmethyl venlafaxine (ODV). The determination ranges of Venlafaxine and O-Desmethyl venlafaxine were between 0.5 – 500 ng/mL.

During the venlafaxine study, all enrolled sows started showing behavioral alterations such as lethargy after the first week of dosing, that evolved in severe gait alteration. The inability to stand up and safely reach feed and water was included as one of the indications, in the ethical protocol approved by the Italian Ministry of Health, to suspend dosing and interrupt the study. At the same time, piglets started showing gastrointestinal alterations such as diarrhea and lack of appetite. Therefore, the study was suspended (during the low dose regimen, 75 mg/day). Already 24 hours after the interruption of dosing, the sows started recovering and were able to stand up, eat and drink, and went back to normal after 2 days.

The results of the plasmatic PK study performed on the sows on the first day of venlafaxine dosing (low dose, 75 mg/day) are represented in Figure 3-30.

Figure 3-30 Quantification of venlafaxine and O-desmethyl venlafaxine in sow's plasma upon first dosing (low dose, 75 mg/day). The graph represents the mean value; error bars indicate the standard error of the mean (SEM).

Descriptive statistics for the quantification of venlafaxine and ODV into maternal plasma and milk samples are reported in Table 3.10 and 3.11 respectively. As previously indicated, data only refer to the low dosing regime (75 mg/day).

Table 3-10 Venlafaxine and ODV quantification (ng/ml) in maternal plasma samples.

		VENLAFAXINE				
		<i>n</i>	Min ng/ml	Max ng/ml	Mean ng/ml	SEM ng/ml
Low Dose 75 mg/day	Pre-venlafaxine	23	0	137.3	35.53	7.95
	1h post	12	2.914	102	40.29	10.63
	3h post	12	8.998	234.5	79.76	19.03
	4h post	11	10.93	305.4	135.1	33.38
	6h post	11	11.74	298.9	78.8	25.53
		O-DESMETHYL VENLAFAXINE				
		<i>n</i>	Min ng/ml	Max ng/ml	Mean ng/ml	SEM ng/ml
	Pre-venlafaxine	23	2.777	132.5	50.71	8.572
	1h post	12	17.28	97.88	51.24	8.101
	3h post	12	36.37	171.6	80.24	11.56
	4h post	11	31.36	198.2	102.8	16.16
	6h post	11	31.5	204.1	77.74	14.39

Table 3-11 Venlafaxine and ODV quantification (ng/ml) in maternal milk samples.

		VENLAFAXINE				
		<i>n</i>	Min ng/ml	Max ng/ml	Mean ng/ml	SEM ng/ml
Low Dose 75 mg/day	Pre-venlafaxine	28	6.796	251.7	75.17	14.21
	1h post	17	4.353	306	89.96	20.74
	3h post	17	17	542.9	167.2	42.35
	4h post	11	0.5328	1289	372.6	114.8
	6h post	13	33.25	870.7	278.1	72.95
		O-DESMETHYL VENLAFAXINE				
		<i>n</i>	Min ng/ml	Max ng/ml	Mean ng/ml	SEM ng/ml
	Pre-venlafaxine	24	10.84	222	114	13.24
	1h post	13	41	272.8	134.3	20.7
	3h post	13	94.09	488	205	29.8
	4h post	11	1.47	595	257.7	56.28
	6h post	13	75.58	483.5	237.4	35.26

Figure 3-31 represents the trends of the concentrations of venlafaxine and ODV in maternal plasma, only for the low dosing regimen (75 mg/day); the results of the statistical analysis (Kruskal-Wallis test followed by the multiple comparisons post-hoc test) performed to assess differences between timepoints are also included. The plasmatic peak was recorded 4 hours after administration for both venlafaxine and its main metabolite.

Figure 3-31 Graphical representation of the concentrations of venlafaxine (A) and ODV (B) in sows' plasma upon oral administration (different letters indicate differences between timepoints, $p < 0.05$).

Figure 3-32. represents the trend of the medicine and its metabolite in milk samples. The behaviour of venlafaxine and ODV is identical in milk, with a marked peak four hours after administration.

Figure 3-32 Graphical representation of the concentrations of venlafaxine (A) and ODV (B) in sows' milk upon oral administration (different letters indicate differences between timepoints, $p < 0.05$).

As for piglets, venlafaxine itself was always below the lower limit of detection, while O-desmethyl venlafaxine was quantifiable in 22 out of 30 samples. The levels of ODV in piglets' plasma are represented in Figure 3-33, alongside the comparison with the corresponding levels in milk. Also in this case, piglets' exposure seems to be extremely low.

Figure 3-33 O-desmethyl venlafaxine levels in piglets' plasma collected before and 4h after maternal administration and comparison with corresponding milk levels.

3.2.6 Amoxicillin GLP-compliant trial (LABCORP)

Figure 3-34 Quantification of amoxicillin in sow's milk and plasma upon intramuscular administrations (time normalized to the time after last dose). Solid line represents the mean concentration-time profile.

3.2.7 Cassette-dosing trial (LABCORP)

This study is still on-going at the Harrogate Labcorp facility at the conclusion of the ConcePTION project. When concluded, samples will be shipped to Bionotus and results will be available in January 2025. When this data is available in early 2025, it will be incorporated into the BB for the EMA QA meeting that will occur in 2025 after the conclusion of the project.

3.2.8 Milk/Plasma Ratio calculation animal model vs human

The *in vivo* model seems to be a promising tool for predicting maternal systemic exposure, milk medicine concentration, and infant systemic medicine concentrations. Furthermore, the M/P ratio observed in Göttingen Minipigs and reported for humans in literature (Kafetzis et al., 1981; Wilkerson et al., 2021; Korsgren et al., 2007; Briggs et al., 2005; Eyal et al., 2010; Gardiner et al., 2003; Hale et al., 2002; Ilett et al., 1998 and 2002) showed good correlation across the 4 medicines tested (Figure 3.35). Importantly, ultimate verification of the *in vivo* model against clinical (human) lactation data will be possible based on newly collected data as part of ConcePTION WP4 for the same model medicines.

Figure 3-35 M/P ratios observed in Göttingen Minipigs versus reported for humans in literature.

As a whole the animal lactation model in Göttingen Minipig sows, has been shown to determine maternal systemic exposure, milk medicine concentration, and infant systemic medicine concentrations as a prediction of human maternal and infant exposure to a medicine. Considering the 4 medicines tested, it was shown that amoxicillin, metformin, levocetirizine and venlafaxine, including its main metabolite O-desmethyl venlafaxine, were always above the quantification limits in sows' plasma and milk, with the expected exception of the samples collected before the first dosing. This finding suggests that all test compounds were able to cross the blood/mammary barrier into milk, yet with differences amongst medicines. Indeed, some showed a widest time delay between the plasmatic and milk peak than others. On the other hand, the levels of medicines in the piglets' bloodstream were not always above the lower limit of detection, once again with different patterns across medicines, suggesting different transfer capabilities.

3.3 Population PK analysis

A total of 123 plasma and 85 milk samples were obtained from three lactating Göttingen Minipigs in the study conducted by UNIBO; 215 plasma and 169 milk samples were obtained from 6 lactating Göttingen

Minipigs in the study conducted by LABCORP. Data from 9 plasma samples and four milk samples in UNIBO's study were excluded from the population pharmacokinetic (PK) analysis: three plasma samples and four milk samples had concentrations below the lower limit of quantification (LLOQ), and 7 plasma samples (including one below LLOQ) were from a minipig that developed an abrupt disease, which resolved on the same day. Data from 9 plasma and 33 milk samples in LABCORP's study were excluded from the population PK analysis: 9 plasma and 14 milk samples had concentrations below LLOQ; 19 milk samples did not meet bioanalytical acceptance criteria. Consequently, 114 plasma concentrations and 81 milk concentrations from UNIBO's study and 206 plasma concentrations and 136 milk concentrations from LABCORP's study were included in the population PK analysis.

A two-compartment model with zero-order absorption and linear elimination was selected as the final model to describe the plasma and milk concentrations of amoxicillin in the lactating postpartum Göttingen Minipigs. In this model structure, the central compartment was linked to the milk compartment via bidirectional first-order transfer. To describe the increasing pattern observed in plasma concentrations over time, days postpartum (DPP) was implemented as a regressor that allowed the volume of distribution to change over time, as shown in Equation 24 where TV denotes time-varying. The parameter estimates from the final model were presented in Table 3-12.

$$V_{TV} = V \times DPP^{(\beta_{DPP-V})} \quad (\text{Equation 24})$$

The goodness-of-fit (GOF) plots (Figure 3-36) and prediction-corrected visual predictive check (pcVPC) plots (Figure 3-37) demonstrated that the model was capable of describing the plasma and milk data. Although the GOF plots indicated some level of misspecification, the majority of the observations were in line with the model's predictions. In a virtual population receiving repeated doses of 303.8 mg (assumed flat-dose based on mean bodyweight) amoxicillin once daily (Figure 3-38), based on the median simulated concentrations of the virtual population following the last 5 doses, the area under the curve (AUC_{τ}) of amoxicillin in plasma and milk were $11788 \pm 432 \text{ ng}\cdot\text{h}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ and $2782 \pm 128 \text{ ng}\cdot\text{h}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$, respectively. The estimated milk intake volume of each GMP piglet was $17.2 \text{ mL}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$, and the daily milk intake volume by a GMP piglet was $797 \text{ mL}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$ ($0.797 \text{ L}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$). Based on these values, the estimated milk-to-plasma (M/P) ratio, daily infant dosage (DID), and relative infant dose (RID) were 0.236, $0.0937 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$, and 1.34%, respectively (Table 3-13).

Table 3-12 Parameter estimates of amoxicillin in lactating postpartum Göttingen Minipigs by the final PopPK model. Abbreviation: RSE, relative standard error.

Parameters		Estimate	RSE (%)
Fixed effects	Tk0 (h)	1.25	5.53
	V (L)	92.48	20.2
	β_{DPP-V}	0.47	12.9
	CL ($\text{L}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$)	10.52	9.88
	Q ($\text{L}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$)	1.37	9.45
	V_{BM} (L)	78.81	44.9
	CL_{BM} ($\text{L}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$)	4.34	21.3
Random effects	ω_V	0.39	26.3
	ω_{CL}	0.28	26.9

	ω_{CLBM}	0.49	33.1
Correlation	V and CL	0.63	38.3
Log-additive error	Plasma ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$)	0.49	4.06
	Milk ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$)	1.04	4.92

Figure 3-36 Goodness-of-fit plots of the final PopPK model for amoxicillin in lactating postpartum Göttingen Minipigs plasma (A-D) and milk (E-H). Abbreviation: PPRED, population prediction; IPRED, individual prediction; IWRES, individual weighted residuals.

Figure 3-37 Prediction-corrected visual predictive checks of the final PopPK model for amoxicillin in lactating postpartum Göttingen Minipigs plasma and milk.

Figure 3-38 Simulated concentrations of amoxicillin in plasma (pink) and milk (blue) in lactating postpartum Göttingen Minipigs. The solid line represents the median simulated concentrations, and the shaded area represents the 90% confidence intervals.

Table 3-13 Simulated milk-to-plasma (M/P) ratio and infant dose in Göttingen Minipigs: The predicted values were estimated from the median simulated plasma and milk profiles following the last 5 doses.

	Based on AUC	Based on Cmax
M/P ratio	0.236	0.174
DID (mg·kg ⁻¹ ·day ⁻¹)	0.0937	0.117
RID (%)	1.34	1.67

The population PK analysis was an extension of the *in vivo* study. Using the amoxicillin plasma and milk data sets obtained in the lactating postpartum Göttingen Minipigs, the developed population PK model successfully captured the pharmacokinetic characteristics of amoxicillin in lactating Göttingen Minipigs. The model-based simulation indicated that the exposure of piglets to amoxicillin through breastfeeding was minimal, suggesting a low risk of adverse events. This conclusion is reinforced by the absence of adverse events in the piglets observed during the study.

3.4 Physiology-Based Pharmacokinetic (PBPK) models

PBPK models were developed for 11 medicines using Simcyp software. Detailed descriptions for the model development and the evaluation of their predictive performance are provided in drug-specific reports, which are available upon request.

The evaluation of the predictive performance indicated that the adult PBPK models were able to capture the pharmacokinetic behavior of the drugs in healthy volunteer.

The calculated M/P ratios (AUC-based or relying on the log transformed phase-distribution model) were comparable with the reported values in literature

The daily infant dose value (mg/kg/day) was calculated based on the human milk average concentration at steady state assuming a high needed therapeutic dose for each drug assumed to the maternal PBPK model. Table 3-14 presents the daily infant dose (DID) (mg/kg/day) and relative infant dose (RID, %) assuming different volumes of milk intake.

These calculations reflect the amount of medication that an infant is exposed to via breastfeeding during maternal pharmacotherapy at steady state.

Table 3-14 Daily infant dosage (DID) and relative infant dose (RID) values for 10 medicines

Drug	Maternal dose (mg) / administration regimen	Predicted Average concentration in milk (mg/L)	Predicted M/P ratio ^c	DID ^d (mg/kg/day) (RID, %)	
				Milk volume 150 mL	Milk volume 200 mL
Amoxicillin ^a	1000/TID	0.66 (0.62-0.69)	0.14 (0.13-0.14)	0.10 (0.22)	0.13 (0.29)
Levetiracetam ^a	1500/BID	47.44 (45.56-49.41)	1.37 (1.37-1.38)	7.12 (15.60)	9.49 (20.80)
Caffeine ^a	100/TID	3.17 (2.80-3.59)	1.41 (1.41-1.42)	0.48 (10.43)	0.63 (13.90)
Zidovudine ^a	300/BID	0.57 (0.51-0.61)	1.30 (1.29-1.30)	0.09 (0.94)	0.11 (1.25)
Metformin ^a	500/BID	0.11 (0.11-0.12)	0.16 (0.162-1.16)	0.017 (0.11)	0.023 (0.15)
Cetirizine ^a	10/QD	0.025 (0.019-0.034)	0.16 (0.14-0.19)	0.00375 (2.47)	0.005 (3.29)
Tenofovir ^a	300/QD	0.016 (0.014-0.017)	0.08 (0.084-0.0085)	0.0023 (0.05)	0.0031 (0.07)
Valproic acid ^b	2100/QD	4.13 (3.96-4.30)	0.05	0.62 (1.94)	0.83 (2.59)
Sertraline ^b	50/QD	0.05 (0.043-0.051)	1.62	0.00705 (0.93)	0.0094 (1.24)
Nevirapine ^b	200/BID	6.09 (5.79-6.40)	1.06	0.91 (15.02)	1.22 (20.03)
Sildenafil ^b	20/TID	0.0053 (0.0049-0.0057)	0.08	0.00075 (0.08)	0.001 (0.11)

BID: twice a day administration; DID: daily infant dosage; RID: relative infant dosage; M/P ratio using permeability-limited model and average concentration in milk values are shown as geometric mean (GM) and 90% confidence interval (CI). ^a lactation PBPK model developed using permeability-limited model; ^b lactation PBPK model using perfusion-limited model; ^c the M/P ratio was estimated (i) based on the ratio of AUC_{milk} over AUC_{plasma} (Equation 11) for permeability-limited models and (ii) using the log transformed phase-distribution by Atkinson and Begg (Equations 12 and 13) for perfusion-limited models ^d daily infant dosage estimated assuming milk volume of 150-200mL

In summary, the lactation PBPK models resulted in adequate predictions of maternal plasma and human milk concentration time profiles for 11 medicines. The framework for PBPK model development and evaluation can be used to simulate the human milk concentration and calculate predicted infant doses for virtually any (small molecule) medicine. In addition, these models will serve as starting points for

developing PBPK models describing the pharmacokinetics (PK) of biologicals, such as monoclonal antibodies.

Another step in the refinement of the presently developed lactation models will include the implementation of experimentally determined permeability data for the blood milk barrier (ongoing work, the predictive performance did not show improvement over the semi-mechanistic approach, indicating that further refinement is required).

The characterization data obtained with the newly developed human and minipig primary mammary epithelial cell culture models already illustrated representativity of the *in vivo* blood-milk barrier. In addition, the *in vitro* transport data obtained so far with model medicines (e.g., illustrating differentiation between low and high permeability compounds) demonstrate the unique utility of these state-of-the-art *in vitro* models, for accurate and rapid determination of plasma-milk transfer rates of medicines and medicine candidates across this blood-milk barrier (see section 3.1). Initial data confirmed in replicate experiments and analyses.

4 Conclusion

Currently, there is no well-developed non-clinical model accepted by health authorities that can be used by pharmaceutical companies and researchers to predict medicine secretion into human milk. Of the standard reproductive toxicology studies conducted during the development of a new drug candidate, the pre- and postnatal developmental toxicity study is the only one that includes a lactation phase.

Within the IMI ConcePTION project, WP3 defined the above-described non-clinical strategies for providing quantitative insights regarding drug milk secretion, as well as to predict drug exposure in breastfed infants.

The characterization data obtained with the newly developed human and minipig primary mammary epithelial cell culture models already illustrated representativity of the *in vivo* blood-milk barrier. Primary human mammary epithelial cells and minipig mammary epithelial cells formed a tight monolayer, suitable for transport studies. The models can distinguish between high and low permeability compounds and demonstrate the unique utility of these state-of-the-art *in vitro* models, for accurate and rapid determination of plasma-milk transfer rates of medicines and medicine candidates across this blood-milk barrier.

The permeability coefficients will be used as input for the PBPK models. This will enable the prediction of human milk concentrations of medicines, even in the absence of clinical data. However, while the mechanistic feasibility of integrating *in vitro* permeability values generated in a human mammary epithelial cell culture models was shown, the predictive performance is not improved compared to the semi-mechanistic approach indicating further refinement is needed.

The *in vivo* model serves as a pivotal tool to assess medicine exposure both in maternal plasma and milk and offspring plasma, leading to reliable high resolution PK data. Such datasets not only provide information regarding medicines but will also be instrumental in improving and refine generic templates and workflows for simulation-based prediction of medicine milk excretion in humans. Population PK analysis is used to describe the PK characteristics and variabilities of a medicine in the lactating postpartum population of the species selected as the *in vivo* model. The derived model can be used to simulate the possible infant dose.

The first *in vivo* study with amoxicillin has been pivotal to assess the sustainability of the proposed procedures both in terms of animal compliance with the repeated samplings during such a peculiar and stressful physiological timeframe as postpartum, and in terms of feasibility of milk collection. Indeed, standardized procedures for milk collection in sows were lacking. The use of a peripherally inserted long-term catheter allowed a critical refinement of the experimental procedures requiring repeated blood samplings, minimizing stress that may have led to lactation suppression. Based on the results obtained, the protocol was well tolerated both by animals, that gained confidence and trust during the preliminary training sessions, and by the staff performing the procedures. Considering such results and the expected standards of the pharmaceutical industry field, the following trials were only performed on Göttingen Minipigs sows. Again, the trials were very well tolerated by animals, also thanks to the training protocol established by Ellegaard in preparation of the first pilot study, and by the operators.

The lactation PBPK models resulted in adequate predictions of maternal plasma and milk concentration time profiles for all medicines, The framework for PBPK model development and evaluation can be used to simulate human milk concentration time profiles and calculate predicted infant doses for virtually any

(small molecule) medicine. In addition, these models will represent starting points for PBPK models describing PK of biologicals (such as monoclonal antibodies).

All methods used, including *in vitro*, *in vivo* and PBPK models, have demonstrated the ability to adequately determine the maternal systemic exposure, milk medicine concentration, and infant systemic medicine concentrations, both independently and in combination, which would support recommendations for breastfeeding in the lactation section of the (small molecule) medicine's label or at least a recommendation that *in vivo* experiments with Gottingen Minipigs would be supportive.

Based on the current results and the interpretation of those results, this non-clinical platform/workflow demonstrated that the models shown *in vitro*, *in vivo* and *in silico* carry the promise to allow a reliable prediction of medicine concentration in human milk and could serve as best practices to inform risk assessment on medication use during lactation also independently.

The WP3 team believes that the conclusions of the studies would adequately support the qualification of *in vitro*, *in vivo* and *in silico* models presented for predicting the concentrations of medicines in human milk. The team is seeking Qualification advice from EMA and supports the establishment of these models as innovative, state-of the art methods to determine the concentrations of different medicines in human milk and would therefore be interested to request a Qualification Opinion by the Agency.

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